

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Framework for the Development of Open Science and Scholarly Communication Training

OPERAS PLUS DELIVERABLE 6.3

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Deliverable 6.3

Framework for the development of Open Science and Scholarly Communication Training

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Abstract

This document presents a structured framework for developing training on Open Science, open scholarly communication and service use within the OPERAS research infrastructure. It outlines a modular, adaptable toolkit based on the ADDIE methodology, integrating principles of FAIRness and Open Educational Resources. The framework supports diverse stakeholders in designing, delivering, and evaluating high-quality training, contributing to OPERAS' strategic goals and its transition toward becoming a sustainable European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC).

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Abbreviations / Acronyms

Abbreviation	
ADDIE	Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
NN	National Node
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
ToT	Train of Trainers

Executive summary

The purpose of this document is to present a comprehensive framework for the

development of training in Open Science (OS) and open scholarly communication within the OPERAS research infrastructure. As a federated infrastructure, OPERAS connects diverse national communities while fostering a unified vision for open science, research integrity, inclusivity, and bibliodiversity, supporting the essential role of open access in knowledge circulation. National Nodes identify community-specific needs, promote services, mediate between European and national priorities, and advocate for inclusion and collaboration. They ensure that OPERAS remains responsive to regional diversity while amplifying national contributions at the European level.

As OPERAS progresses toward becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), it has recognized the need for consistent, high-quality training to support its services, national nodes, and broader Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research community. In this scenario, training is a strategic and essential component of OPERAS, crucial for empowering users, enhancing service effectiveness, supporting national nodes, and ensuring the sustainability and impact of the research infrastructure. Far from being a secondary function, training acts as a transformative lever that enables OPERAS to promote open science, meet evolving standards, and strengthen its role in the European scholarly communication ecosystem.

OPERAS has supported training in Open Science (OS) and Diamond Open Access (OA) through various funded projects like Skills4EOSC, DIAMAS, and CRAFT-OA, which provide a strong foundation to build upon. However, existing training for service end-users remains fragmented and lacks a cohesive structure. There is a need for a coordinated, integrated training framework that combines practical service use with broader OS principles, FAIR compliance, and the Diamond OA publishing best practices, among other topics.

This deliverable (D6.3) is designed to support this goal by offering a structured methodology—based on the ADDIE model—for designing, delivering, and evaluating training initiatives that are inclusive, scalable, and aligned with Open Science principles. The framework is intended for those creating, adapting, and managing training content, providing tools to identify needs, define learning outcomes, select delivery methods, and assess effectiveness.

The framework for developing training for OPERAS takes the form of a toolkit composed of a series of articles and guides that provides people with a methodology and guides them step by step when they need to implement training. This format was chosen to offer more autonomy and flexibility to address different needs and keep up with further developments. The framework complies with Open Educational Resources (OER) principles and employs the FAIR-by-Design methodology to accomplish openness and FAIRness.

The next steps for implementing the OPERAS framework for training involve developing training programmes focused on OPERAS services. Equally important is the establishment of meaningful collaborations across OPERAS infrastructure. Shared

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values, clear roles, co-creation activities, and transparent documentation foster participation and engagement. Invest in monitoring activities is essential to maintain relevance and quality. This can be achieved by aligning evaluation metrics with the framework's goals to track performance and inform improvements. Finally, the framework is designed to support both scalability and long-term sustainability due to its structure that allows for standardizing processes while keeping content flexible and adaptable to different needs. The future actions should enable the fulfilment of those objectives.

Introduction

1. Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to present a comprehensive framework for the development of training in Open Science (OS) and open scholarly communication within the OPERAS research infrastructure. As OPERAS progresses toward becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), it recognizes the need for consistent, high-quality training to support its services, national nodes, and broader Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research community. At the core of OPERAS lies its service-oriented approach¹, designed to support the entire scholarly communication lifecycle.

This deliverable (D6.3) is designed to support that objective by offering a structured methodology—based on the ADDIE model²—for designing, delivering, and evaluating training initiatives that are inclusive, scalable, and aligned with Open Science principles.

The scope of the document encompasses both the analysis of the current context including existing training materials and initiatives and the description of the methodology. It identifies key stakeholders and their diverse training needs to ensure relevant and impactful training design, explains how the framework, based on ADDIE model, is fit for a learner-centred approach and enables reuse across varied roles and institutions. It also describes how the framework was collaboratively developed as a toolkit composed of articles and templates.

Finally, it discusses future steps including the establishment of collaborations, the definition of evaluation metrics and discusses strategies for scaling and sustaining training initiatives.

¹ Holsinger, S. (2023). OPERAS Initial Technical Design (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 5.1) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289073>

² ADDIE is an instructional design model. The acronym stands for Analysis, Design, Delivery, Implementation and Evaluation. This model allows for the design and implementation of training in an iterative way, allowing the integration of feedback at multiple stages and ensuring flexibility during the whole process.

2. Brief OPERAS overview

OPERAS is the European Research Infrastructure dedicated to supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It contributes significantly³ to the European Research Area (ERA) by federating and coordinating scattered resources across Europe to better address the specific scholarly communication needs of SSH researchers. As a federated infrastructure, OPERAS connects diverse national communities while fostering a unified vision for open science, research integrity, inclusivity, and bibliodiversity, supporting the essential role of open access policies in knowledge circulation⁴.

2.1 OPERAS services

At the core of OPERAS lies its service-oriented approach⁵, designed to support the entire scholarly communication lifecycle. These services are grouped into eight strategic categories: Discovery, Analytics, Quality Assurance, Research4Society, Multilingualism, Training, Operational Services, and Collaboration Tools.

GoTriple⁶ discovery service enables users to discover and reuse open scholarly resources in multiple languages and connect with other authors and researchers in SSH.

VERA⁷ allows researchers to collaborate on citizen science projects, providing support throughout the entire project process.

Pathfinder⁸ helps Editors and Press/Publishing Directors to discover the services that they need in the full editorial process.

OPERAS Metrics⁹ collects usage and impact metrics from various sources related to published Open Access books that can be accessed, displayed and analysed from a single access point.

³ Council Conclusions on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science, 10 June 2022 welcomed the setting up of both open access platforms and university presses and of dedicated research infrastructures such as OPERAS in the framework of European approach and capacities for academic publishing and scholarly communication. [Research assessment and implementation of Open Science - Council conclusions \(adopted on 10 June 2022\)](#)

⁴ The Council conclusions on Research Infrastructures also recognized the important role of open access policies in knowledge circulation Council Conclusions on Research Infrastructures, 2 December 2022. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-15429-2022-INIT/en/pdf>

⁵ Holsinger, S. (2023). OPERAS Initial Technical Design (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 5.1) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289073>

⁶ <https://gotriple.eu>

⁷ <https://vera.operas-eu.org>

⁸ <https://pathfinder.operas-eu.org/>

⁹ <https://metrics.operas-eu.org>

PRISM¹⁰ (Peer Review Information Service for Monographs) improves transparency and trust in Open Access book publishing by providing standardised information about the peer-review process.

Hypothèses¹¹ provides a space for SSH research blogs, fostering innovative formats of scholarly communication and offering multilingual content.

Mondaecus¹², a translation service, provides a collaborative environment for researchers and professionals to translate and edit scientific documents in multiple languages.

Innovation Lab¹³ designs and implements scalable, sustainable cutting-edge solutions for open scholarly communication while cultivating a culture of innovation within OPERAS and the SSH community.

2.2 OPERAS community: The National Nodes

OPERAS community remains central to this federated model and the National Nodes strategically connects OPERAS and local research ecosystems. National Nodes identify community-specific needs, promote services, mediate between European and national priorities, and advocate for inclusion and collaboration. They ensure that OPERAS remains responsive to regional diversity while amplifying national contributions at the European level.

OPERAS National Nodes play an important role in building capacity of the OPERAS community by identifying specific support and training needs at local and regional levels, ensuring that capacity gaps are recognized and addressed. They are also responsible for providing training on OPERAS services and related topics, facilitating the community's understanding and effective use of the infrastructure.

2.3 OPERAS Strategies and Objectives

OPERAS' mission—to make Open Science a reality for Social Sciences and Humanities research and to ensure that knowledge is freely accessible to benefit society at large—drives every aspect of its development. Central to fulfilling this mission is the transition toward becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), a step that not only guarantees legal and financial stability but also establishes OPERAS as a permanent, high-quality, Pan-European structure. To support this transformation, OPERAS has articulated a strategic plan grounded in four interrelated pillars: redesigning the scholarly communication ecosystem, empowering the community, supporting bibliodiversity, and fostering quality.

The OPERAS strategy plays a vital role in achieving ERIC status, as it aligns long-term

¹⁰ <https://www.doabooks.org/en/librarians/prism>

¹¹ <https://hypotheses.org/>

¹² <https://mondaecus.com/>

¹³ <https://lab.operas-eu.org/>

vision with practical implementation. Two central themes of the strategy emphasize the importance of training: improving the overall quality and efficiency of the scholarly Open Access (OA) communication ecosystem, and empowering communities to actively shape and participate in it. Empowerment, in particular, is intrinsically tied to training. By equipping SSH communities with the knowledge and skills necessary to engage with Open Science practices, adopt FAIR principles, and deliver high-quality services, OPERAS fosters the cultural and operational shifts required for systemic change.

3. Importance of training for OPERAS

Training is one of the pillars of OPERAS' mission and service portfolio. As both a stand-alone category and a cross-cutting element within all activities, training ensures that researchers, institutions, and service providers can effectively engage with open science tools and practices.

Training plays a critical role in the development and sustainability of a research infrastructure's service portfolio. It not only empowers users to navigate and utilize services more efficiently but also significantly enhances their overall experience and satisfaction. When users are well trained, they understand the full scope and value of a service, which leads to higher retention, reduced frustration, and fewer support requests—ultimately saving time and operational costs for both the research infrastructure and its service providers. Moreover, well-trained users are more likely to become advocates for the services and the infrastructure itself, promoting wider adoption and reinforcing the impact of the services.

Training is also essential for the effectiveness and sustainability of OPERAS national nodes, as it underpins many of their core activities. In their role as intermediaries between national communities and the European-level infrastructure, national nodes are responsible for presenting and integrating OPERAS services within national research ecosystems. This means that national nodes must disseminate expertise and foster shared practices, both of which depend on structured and informal training efforts. National nodes are equally responsible for translating local needs into aligned responses—an effort that often requires knowledge transfer and the development of specific skills. Training enables national nodes to deliver targeted solutions, evaluate impact, and ensure broad, equitable access to OPERAS services through effective onboarding and support. Capacity-building is also central to initiatives like promoting multilingualism, supporting bibliodiversity, and co-developing best practices. In this way, training is not just a supporting activity but a strategic enabler that enhances the national nodes' ability to connect, coordinate, and contribute meaningfully to the OPERAS infrastructure.

This training framework is, therefore, not an accessory but a strategic lever for transformation. It enables the OPERAS community to implement best practices, adapt to evolving standards, and sustain high-quality, open scholarly communication systems. As OPERAS advances toward becoming an ERIC, its commitment to training

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ensures that the infrastructure remains inclusive, responsive, and aligned with the needs of researchers and institutions across Europe, ultimately strengthening its position as a cornerstone of the European Open Science landscape.

Part A – Development of the Training Framework

1. Understanding the context

OPERAS has been involved in the implementation of training on OS practices and on diamond OA publishing. These efforts have been coordinated through different funded projects. This context highlights, thus, the opportunity to build on existing efforts rather than starting from scratch. Projects, such as Skills4EOSC, DIAMAS, and CRAFT-OA, have already developed high-quality training materials that address key needs of researchers and publishers.

Regarding services, OPERAS portfolio has been through steady development. Some training for service end-users exist but they remain fragmented, lacking a unifying structure or delivery mechanism. This calls for a coordinated effort to consolidate, align, and supplement these initiatives, ensuring a cohesive and complementary curriculum that serves end-users effectively. Importantly, developing such a type of training does not mean focusing solely on how to use services. Rather, it means combining service-specific instruction with foundational training on Open Science, FAIR data, multilingualism, Diamond OA model, etc., domains that directly influence the effective use and long-term value of the services themselves.

The framework for the development of training within OPERAS must be understood in this federated context and it must encompass OPERAS broader strategic ambition to support open scholarly communication in the SSH, and its ongoing transition toward becoming an ERIC. As OPERAS continues to further develop its service portfolio and strengthen its national nodes, training becomes the mechanism through which users, providers, and partners gain the skills and confidence to engage effectively with services, while adopting open science practices, implementing FAIR principles, and supporting the OA diamond publishing model.

The following sections describe the training contribution coming from different initiatives.

1.1 Open Science, Research Data Management and FAIR Principles for Social Sciences and Humanities Researchers

In the context of the Skills4EOSC¹⁴ project, a complete Train of Trainers (ToT) on Open Science, Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR principles for SSH researchers was developed. The course consists of a learning path with the corresponding training material based on research workflows within SSH disciplines. It introduces the necessary skills and competencies to support an open and collaborative research methodology. The Train of Trainers was developed through an in-depth analysis of requirements, standards, and a pilot training event to validate and refine the materials based on stakeholder feedback.

The training program was designed using a structured workflow that began with defining the competencies and skills to be developed, aimed for SSH researchers and support staff interested in becoming OS, RDM, FAIR trainers. Learning outcomes were derived from the Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles, or Minimum Viable Skillset (White, A., & Green, D., 2025), which defines the core competencies researchers need to support Open Science practices. The instructional design followed the FAIR-By-Design methodology (Filiposka et al., 2023a) to ensure training materials were findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, with each step undergoing FAIR compliance checks. Co-design efforts included feedback from other SSH research infrastructures (DARIAH, CESSDA, and CLARIN). The program was aligned with the research and data lifecycle, focusing on data management workflows and linking them to OS-aligned publication strategies.

The overall workflow allows continuous development and level adaptations in the key areas—OS practices, RDM and FAIR compliance—by addressing a spectrum of identified challenges faced by the SSH community, such as:

- Diversity of data and formats, each data type requiring specific curation methods, rendering more complex the efforts to implement standardized methodologies.
- Ethical and legal aspects as SSH research often involves sensitive and personal data, which are subject to ethical guidelines and data protection regulations, requiring a more significant effort to make data openly accessible and interoperable while maintaining compliance with legal requirements.
- Limited skills, considering that training in digitally-oriented practices is not a standard practice within the SSH disciplines, the skills gap results in difficulties in ensuring data interoperability and reusability, as well as in using digital tools and services.

¹⁴ Skills4EOSC: European Commission funded project aiming at producing a pan-European network of competence centres to speed up the training of European researchers and harmonise the training of new professional figures for scientific data management (<https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>)

- Lack of awareness on FAIR RDM and OS principles as many SSH researchers might not be adequately informed about the benefits of adopting OS practices and the ways that FAIR practices can facilitate their research and enhance the visibility, reproducibility, and impact of their work.

The training was delivered in synchronous and asynchronous mode and then it was adapted to self-paced format and is available on the Skills4EOSC Moodle platform¹⁵. The complete programme is detailed in Annex 1.

1.2 Open Access Diamond Publishing

In the context of the DIAMAS project¹⁶, a comprehensive training programme for journal editors and Institutional Publishing Service Providers across the ERA was developed.

The training programme addresses skill gaps identified in earlier project phases and reported trough:

- the mapping of publishing practices across Europe, identifying common challenges and needs within the institutional and Diamond OA publishing ecosystem (Armengou et al, 2023),
- the gap analysis between the standard recommendations for OA diamond publishing and actual institutional publishing practices (Brun et al. 2023).

The programme objective is to support publishers in adopting the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS, Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2024) and strengthen institutional Diamond OA publishing practices. The design of the programme drew upon prior DIAMAS outputs — specifically the Toolsuite (Armengou et al., 2024i) and Guidelines (Armengou et al., 2024ii) — repackaging them into a modular, self-paced online training workflow. The training programme is available on the EDCH Moodle platform¹⁷. The complete programme is detailed in Annex 2.

The Craft-OA¹⁸ project produced two training-related outputs: a reusable curriculum (Kupreyev et al., 2024) and a training toolkit for Diamond OA publishing.

The curriculum¹⁹ provides a comprehensive framework for upskilling training focusing on technical publication standards. It is modular and was designed for diverse stakeholders in OA publishing, such as journal editors, reviewers, and institutional publishing service and technical providers. The curriculum addresses varied publishing environments by recommending training topics, detailing their content,

¹⁵ <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>

¹⁶ DIAMAS: European Commission funded project that aims at delivering an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable institutional OA scholarly publication ecosystem for the ERA (<https://diamasproject.eu/>)

¹⁷ <https://training.diamas.org>

¹⁸ CRAFT-OA: European Commission funded project focusing on improving the technical and organisational infrastructure of Diamond OA (<https://www.craft-oa.eu/>)

¹⁹ <https://craft-oa.gitbook.io/d2.2-curriculum-for-upskilling-trainings>

referencing existing materials, and offering practical guidance for structuring sessions. Each topic is linked to a target audience, skill level, and relevant FAIR principle. A curriculum checklist serves as a flexible tool to guide the development of tailored training programs.

The training material focuses especially on technical standards for institutional OA publishing, and builds on earlier work identifying FAIR-compliant technical standards and the challenges faced by the Diamond OA community in implementing them. The material is organized into categories—Identifiers, Metadata, Content, Website Features, and Overarching—and is designed to support the adoption of best practices. It is presented as a toolkit²⁰ that contains not only training material, but also training sessions and information about training events.

1.3 Service end-users

As the foundations regarding OS practices and Diamond OA publishing are set, the next step to fully apprehend the context for developing a training framework for OPERAS consists in understanding end-user training.

End-user training refers to the process of equipping individuals (such as researchers, authors, editorial managers, institutional staff, data providers, etc.) with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively and efficiently use a technology, platform, or service. In the case of research infrastructures, it ensures that users not only know how to access and operate a service but also understand its purpose, potential, and alignment with the RI's mission and values.

The importance of end-user training goes far beyond simple onboarding (Dolores et., 2015; Farias & Resende, 2020). Its primary objectives include improving user experience, building confidence in navigating systems, and enhancing overall productivity. When users are properly trained, they make more efficient use of services, which leads to reduced frustration, fewer support requests, and greater satisfaction. This in turn boosts user retention, increases adoption rates, and ultimately strengthens the return on investment for the RI. Well-informed users are also more likely to become advocates for the services, contributing to the broader impact and visibility of the infrastructure. Critically, when users understand and experience the full value of a service, it directly supports the RI's performance metrics and long-term sustainability.

To ensure effective implementation, end-user training should follow a set of best practices. These include conducting a thorough needs assessment, tailoring content to specific user groups and learning styles, and clearly aligning training goals with broader strategic objectives. Involving subject matter experts helps ensure the relevance and accuracy of content. Employing diverse content formats, ranging from video tutorials, to interactive modules, passing by step-by-step guides and face-to-face workshops, can enhance engagement and retention. Addressing

²⁰ <https://service.tib.eu/toern/course/section.php?id=223>

common challenges like user resistance to change, as well as measuring training impact, are also essential for long-term success. Ultimately, high-quality end-user training is not an optional add-on but a core component of service development and user engagement within any sustainable research infrastructure. Annex 3 maps potential targets for different training programmes.

The following section details the steps taken to prepare the framework for developing training for OPERAS.

2. Establishing a Methodology

2.1 Target and needs

The federated aspect of OPERAS is the key to the framework. Training initiatives have been and will continue to be federated. Therefore, the framework for developing training offers the blueprint to implement different training programs, addressing multiple topics and targeting varied stakeholders.

As the analysis of the context showed, OPERAS takes part in developing training activities within funded projects. At the same time, the need to develop training for service end-users has also been identified. This means that this framework can be a useful tool for different stakeholders who might be confronted by training requests.

In other words, the framework will primarily be used by those responsible for creating, adapting, delivering, and managing training resources. These users act as the bridge between the infrastructure and the broader research community. To do so, they need some tools to guide them in identifying training needs, establishing learning outcomes, choosing appropriate delivery methods, and evaluating training efficacy. OPERAS experience in different training activities, most of them within funded projects, offers examples of stakeholder groups, the roles they might undertake, and the training needs they might encounter. The table below exemplifies different types of stakeholders who can benefit from the framework for developing training and what needs could be met by it.

Table 1. Examples of users of the framework for developing training

Stakeholder group	Role	Needs
Infrastructure developers and technical staff, including service providers	These stakeholders support training on platform usage, APIs, technical standards, etc.	Integrate technical documentation with training materials. Apply FAIR principles to tutorials.
Data Stewards / Research Data Support Staff	These stakeholders are embedded in research	Develop training tailored to research groups or

	environments, often supporting FAIR data, DMPs, etc.	disciplines. Co-deliver modules alongside domain researchers.
Librarians and Scholarly Communication Officers	These stakeholders can be invited to lead institutional training on publishing, open data, research impact, among other topics. They also act as multipliers and institutional trainers.	Develop or adapt local/institutional training sessions using shared principles. Ensure consistency with broader OS and OA goals.
Open Science Officers or Community Engagement Leads, including National node representatives	These stakeholders promote adoption and culture change across stakeholder groups.	Align training efforts with advocacy and outreach. Build inclusive, community-led training initiatives.
Trainers and Facilitators within the Infrastructure	This type of stakeholders may work for the research infrastructures, in National Nodes, or have project-funded roles.	Reuse and remix modular content. Localize delivery methods based on learner needs.

2.2 A solution applicable to all

The training framework offers a structured, meta-level guide for designing, delivering, and evaluating training in alignment with OPERAS' values, while ensuring consistency, scalability, and quality. It has a modular and flexible structure that allows stakeholders across Open Science and Open Access infrastructures to customize and reuse content, respecting the unique contexts, goals, and capacities of each group. It reduces development effort and ensures materials remain relevant and trustworthy. By providing a shared and adaptable approach, the framework supports collaboration, enables localization and scaling across institutions, and promotes inclusive, accessible, and high-impact training throughout the research ecosystem.

For example, the different stakeholders' groups can use the framework to overcome challenges such as:

- Infrastructure technical staff and service providers deliver consistent onboarding or integration support to service users with low effort while aligning with OS principles.
- SSH data researchers or a research support staff need to train across SSH

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disciplines and adjust to varying levels of data literacy.

- Librarians and scholarly communication professionals need to bridge policy and practice (for instance from Plan S to author rights) and they need to collaborate and co-create resources across institutions.
- Open Science Officers, community engagement leads and National Nodes representatives need to coordinate national or regional outreach where institutional diversity is high, they need to ensure consistency and localization regarding policy context, language, etc.
- Trainers and facilitators within the infrastructure need high-quality, ready-to-run training materials across a range of topics as well as clear guidance on pedagogy, accessibility, and evaluation, ensuring training is effective and inclusive.

Table 2 illustrates how the various features of a common framework for developing training can be beneficial.

Table 2. Benefits of the framework features

Feature of the Framework	Benefits
Modular Structure	Customize content by audience, domain, or depth of knowledge
Flexibility	Support self-paced and synchronous, short or in-depth formats
Open Licensing	Enable reuse, localization, and continuous improvement
Pedagogical Guidance	Ensure training is effective even for non-expert facilitators
Common Vocabulary & Structure	Promote collaboration and reduce fragmentation of effort

2.3 Why ADDIE

This framework follows the ADDIE approach for developing training. The model is widely used by many educational designers and training programmers to develop education and training programs. It appeared in 1975 at the University of Florida. The acronym ADDIE stands for Analyse, Design, Develop, Implement and Evaluate, denoting five phases of a course design (Spatioti et al., 2022). ADDIE model provides a logical sequence of steps for developing high-quality educational programs, adaptable to different formats (distant, face-to-face, self-paced, etc.) and approaches (Abuhassna et al. 2024).

- Analysis: this phase involves identifying variables that must be considered when designing the course (e.g., learner's characteristics, prior knowledge, and available resources).
- Design: this phase identifies learning objectives, as well as the way materials will be created and designed (e.g. content areas that should be covered, in which format the content would be presented: text, audio or video), what technology would be used (e.g. LMS, video, social media).
- Development: this phase involves creating new or adapting existing content, deciding who will produce the content (in-house or outsourced), and uploading content to a website or learning management system (LMS), etc.
- Implementation; this phase refers to the actual delivery of the course, including previous training of learner support staff and learner's assessment.
- Evaluation: the final phase includes collecting feedback to pinpoint improvement areas, informing the design, development, and implementation of the course's next iteration.

In this framework, ADDIE was chosen because it allows a learner-centered approach as the steps keep the learner in the center of the process, from the needs analysis to the evaluation of training effectiveness. Also, it becomes a tool to facilitate collaboration and co-creation of training as training designers and subject matter experts can work together in iterations. The model assures flexibility and continuous refinement of training programme and material, informed by feedback from experts and from the community at large. It is also compatible with other training methodologies which can be used at each step, thereby giving flexibility to trainers to use different approaches.

2.4 Production of the framework

The framework for developing training for OPERAS takes the form of a toolkit composed of a series of articles and guides that provides people with a methodology and guides them step by step when they need to implement training. This format was chosen to offer more autonomy and flexibility to address different needs and keep up with further developments.

The toolkit was produced by T6.4 of WP6 of the OPERAS Plus project. The material was then revised by the community, mostly Open Science and/or training experts.

3. Outline of the toolkit

The toolkit comprises a series of 16 articles and 11 guides and checklists that are organised as a higher-level guideline to assist training designers and instructors in producing training. The templates can be downloaded and they are intended to be a

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starting point for training teams to produce their own programme. Table 4 presents an outline of the toolkit

Table 3. Guidelines for developing training in an OS environment

Training toolsuite		
Phase 1 - Analysis		
Decision	Is training necessary?	
Step	Check the template to perform the needs analysis	
Step	For more info read the articles	Types of analysis Needs analysis
Alternative	If training is not necessary	Try a non-training strategy
	If training is necessary	Do a more thorough analysis
Step	Check the template to describe groups profiles and to create personas	
Step	For more info read the article	Learner's analysis
Step	Check the template to describe and analyse the tasks to be performed	
Step	For more info read the article	Task analysis
Tip	Needs analysis, task analysis and learners' analyses require data collected from different sources. Plan for collecting all the necessary data.	
Step	For more info read the article	Data sources
Tip	Tip: How to choose the best type of analysis for your case?	

	<p>Needs analysis, learners' analysis and task analysis are complementary. The more information you can collect, the better. However, understanding the differences may show what are the most appropriate strategies for your context.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs analysis tells us if we even need training to address the performance problem. • Task analyses help us identify the high-priority actions that we should focus the ensuing training on. Task analysis is also good if we don't know the learners (and we can't easily identify them). • Learner analyses help us make decisions regarding delivery methodology and the level of guidance and background information to provide. 	
Phase 2 - Design		
Decision	Now that the needs analysis is complete, what should learners know or be able to do at the end of the training?	
Step	Check the template to establish your learning outcomes	
Step	For more info read the articles	Learning outcomes Effective learning outcomes Learning outcomes or Learning objectives?
Decision	Once the learning outcomes are established, how will you verify that they have been accomplished?	
Step	Check the template to choose the best assessment method	
Step	For more info read the article	Assessment
Decision	Now, what are the activities the learners will do during the training to accomplish the outcomes? How will the trainer facilitate the learning?	

Step	Check the template to describe the learning experience	
Step	For more info read the article	Learning experience
Step	Certify that these three elements (learning outcomes, assessment and learning experience) are aligned.	
Step	For more info read the article	Alignment and blueprint
Step	For more info read the article	Learning experience
Step	Check the template to prepare the training blueprint	
Step	For more info read the article	Alignment and blueprint
Tip	For more info about a training design method, read the article Backward design	
Tip	Check the FAIR-by-Design methodology to produce training that comply with FAIR principles	
Phase 3 - Development		
Decision	Once you've defined your audience, learning goals, and overall plan in the Analyze and Design stages, the Development stage turns that blueprint into a tangible learning experience. How are you going to do that?	
Step	Check the training development checklist	
Step	For more info read the article	Training development
Phase 4 - Implementation		
Decision	Implementation marks the first time the target audience interacts with the course content and activities. How will this interaction happen? Will the training be tutor-led or self-paced?	
Step	Check the training implementation checklist for both tutor-led training and self-paced training	

Step	For more info read the article	Training implementation
Phase 5- Evaluation		
Decision	Evaluation phase helps teachers and instructors to determine if the learners have understood the content presented to them and helps learners to gauge their own level of understanding. How are you going to evaluate the training efficacy?	
Step	Check the template to prepare the evaluation	
Step	For more info read the articles	Evaluation Designing evaluation questions
Conclusion	Improve and iterate	
	Use the feedback collected during the evaluation phase (but not only) to keep improving the training.	

3.1 Articles

The framework toolkit comprises a series of 16 short articles of 500-1000 words each, with a further reading session that signposts to other resources. The articles also point to other related articles in the toolkit and to the respective templates (guides, tables, checklists) when there is one. The structure of the article was inspired by the one used in the DIAMAS toolsuite (Armengou, C. et al., 2024a). A template can be seen in Annex 4.

3.2 Guides and checklists

Each section of the framework toolsuite, corresponding to ADDIE steps, is accompanied by 11 templates and supporting material (guides, checklists, tables, etc.), that assist the training designer in the different phases of training implantation. The templates can be downloaded and filled out by the design team.

The articles and templates are organized in categories according to ADDIE steps: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation (Table 4).

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Table 4. List of articles and templates of the Framework toolsuite

Framework Category	Article Title	Templates
Analysis	Types of analysis	Needs analysis
	Needs analysis	Learners analysis
	Data sources	Task analysis
	Learner's analysis	
	Task analysis	
Design	Learning outcomes	Learning outcomes
	Effective Learning outcomes	
	Learning objectives or learning outcomes	
	Assessment methods	Assessment
	Learning experience	Learning experience
	Alignment and blueprint	Alignment
	Backward design	Course blueprint
	FAIR-By-Design methodology	
Development	Training development	Training development checklist
Implementation	Training implementation	Training implementation checklist
Evaluation	Evaluation	Evaluation
	Designing evaluation questions	

The complete toolkit with articles and templates constitute Annex 5.

4. Openness of the resources

4.1 Comply with Open Educational Resources Principles

UNESCO's recommendation²¹ on the use of Open Educational Resources (OER) defines OER as "learning, teaching and research materials in any format and medium that reside in the public domain or are under copyright that have been released under an open license, that permit no-cost access, re-use, re-purpose, adaptation and redistribution by others."

David Wiley is one of the pioneers of OER. He and colleagues have first (Hilton et al., 2010) suggested that there are four core principles of open publishing: re-use, re-distribute, revise, and re-mix. They did not create a new type of permission. Rather, they created the 4Rs framework specifically for the purpose of helping people understand and remember the key rights that open content licenses grant them²². With the purpose of the 4Rs framework in mind, David Wiley added a fifth one: retain. According to him, "the original 4Rs are impossible to do without the right to Retain. This makes Retain a fundamental or foundational right, and yet it is completely ignored in the discourse around open."²³

Today, the five principles of OER are the following:

- **Re-use:** The most basic level of openness. People are allowed to use all or part of the work for their own purposes (For example, download an educational video to watch at a later time).
- **Re-distribute:** People can share the work with others (For example, send a digital article by-email to a colleague).
- **Revise:** People can adapt, modify, translate, or change the work (For example, take a book written in English and turn it into a Spanish audio book).
- **Re-mix:** People can take two or more existing resources and combine them to create a new resource (For example, take audio lectures from one course and combine them with slides from another course to create a new derivative work).
- **Retain:** No digital rights management restrictions (DRM); the content is yours to keep, whether you're the author, an instructor using the material, or a student.

4.2 Employ FAIR-by-Design methodology

The 5Rs of OER are high-level principles. To put them into practice, the framework for

²¹

<https://www.unesco.org/en/legal-affairs/recommendation-open-educational-resources-oer?hub=785>

²² <https://opencontent.org/blog/archives/3251>

²³ Idem

developing training recommends the adoption of the FAIR-by-Design methodology (Filiposka, 2023a). This methodology for producing learning materials extends the instructional design process with additional activities focusing on the implementation of the FAIR guiding principles. It consists of a six stage workflow and checklists that help implement the FAIR-by-Design process. The stages are: prepare, discover, design, produce, publish, and verify.

The methodology helps designers and instructors to deal with topics, such as:

- legal issues, intellectual property, licensing and attribution;
- material description and referencing, including the use of a metadata schema and relevant controlled vocabularies and persistent identifiers;
- interoperability issues;
- design and structuring of the learning content, thus ensuring the most appropriate level of granularity for maximum reusability;
- accessibility issues, not only through the definition of access rights, but also ensuring usability by people with disabilities.

Following the FAIR-by-Design workflow ensures efficient collaboration within the community and maximum reusability of developed learning materials.

Part B – Perspectives on use of the training toolkit

1. Next steps

1.1 Develop training for services

The next step consists in employing this framework for developing training to implement a successful service end-user training program in OPERAS. The framework can be used during both planning and execution phases. More specifically, it is a tool to assist in the following steps:

- Identify if training is necessary: this is the first question to be asked and it should not be neglected. Sometimes non-training strategies can be used, such as communication and marketing. It can also help to improve processes and service design.
- Identify the target audience: Clearly define who the target audience is and what their needs are. Understanding the specific requirements of different user groups ensures that the training is relevant and effective. For example, training for the end-user is not the same as training for a service data provider.

- Identify learning outcomes: Once the needs and the target audience are identified, the learning outcomes of the programme can be established.
- Choose a training method: The training method should be suitable for the target audience, such as online training, face-to-face training, or on-the-job training. The chosen method should align with the learners' needs and the organization's resources.
- Develop a training plan: Create a comprehensive training plan that outlines and aligns learning outcomes, assessment methods and modes of instruction. A well-structured plan provides a clear roadmap for the training process. Ensure that the whole training is FAIR-compliant.
- Develop training content: Create training content that is engaging, interactive, and relevant to the target audience. Use a mix of multimedia, real-world scenarios, and interactive elements to enhance the learning experience. Training materials should be FAIR-compliant and have an open licence. The training material can be tested in a pilot phase for a first evaluation.
- Deliver the training: Implement the training program and deliver it to the target audience. Ensure that the delivery method is effective and that learners have access to the necessary resources.
- Evaluate the training: After the training delivery, the whole programme should be assessed for its effectiveness through feedback collection. Performance metrics can be analysed and the results should be used for adjustments and improvement. Use this information to make adjustments and improve the training.

1.2 Establish collaborations

As a federated organisation, OPERAS relies on the establishment of meaningful collaborations. Establishing such collaborations to use a training framework based on ADDIE requires planning, trust-building, and shared ownership across all phases. Collaboration across the different stages of training design and delivery is important because it ensures the framework remains relevant, adaptable, and inclusive. It goes without saying that it brings in diverse expertise (for instance, different domain experts, representatives of different National Nodes, varied roles and stakeholders' groups, etc.). It also enables co-ownership and sustainability of the training ecosystem.

Establishing collaboration is also a way to strengthen existing relationships with other organisations and research infrastructures. It is also a way to connect with National Nodes or thematic clusters.

To establish and sustain collaboration, it is important to start with shared values. It should be framed around openness, inclusivity and mutual benefit. A shared vision statement or even a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) could be used.

Defining roles, contributors, and expectations for each stage can make the

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collaboration clear, it helps to identify phases, to evaluate and value the effort put in it and to coordinate the whole process with transparency in mind. Contributors can be recognised through co-authorship, badges, or public acknowledgment.

Co-creation can be enabled through joint sprints, workshops, or hackathons to co-develop training. Furthermore, the activities can be documented and shared by keeping collaboration processes visible and replicable, sharing templates, and even publishing case studies to help others build similar partnerships.

Annex 6 presents a checklist template to be used when establishing collaborations during different phases of training implementation.

1.3 Establish metrics and evaluate and monitor the training framework

Continuously monitoring and adjusting end user training programs is vital to ensure that it is meeting its goals and objectives and to enhance their effectiveness over time.

After rolling out a training program, it is essential to evaluate and adjust the program regularly to address any emerging issues or gaps. Collecting feedback from users helps identify these gaps and reduces issues later on, ensuring that the training program remains relevant and effective. The effectiveness of a training programme can be measured by evaluating learners’ engagement with the training, knowledge retention (through quizzes or assignments), or a return on investment demonstrating the value of the training programme for the research infrastructure (e.g., more engagement with a particular service or less requests for user support).

To monitor the use and impact of this framework for developing training, it is important to align the metrics with the goals of the framework (Table 5).

Table 5. Types and examples of metrics to monitor the use of the training framework

Topic	Goal	Example
Consistency and quality	Ensures training is well-structured, coherent, and aligns with pedagogical and content standards	percentage of training modules following the framework structure; peer-review score for content quality; alignment of learning outcomes to content and assessment; learner satisfaction with structure and clarity
Flexibility and modularity	Enables adaptation, localization, and reuse of	percentage of materials available in self-contained modules or the number of

	components.	training sessions using customized/adapted versions
Scalability and reuse	Enables wider adoption across institutions, regions, and domains.	number of services with a training programme; number of National Nodes using the framework; number of downloads from a repository; number of trainers trained or certified
Inclusivity and accessibility	Ensures that training is usable and welcoming for all learners, regardless of background or ability.	percentage of content available in multiple languages; number of outreach events targeted to underrepresented groups; percentage of content with accessibility features (alt text, captions, transcripts)
Impact and uptake	Tracks how the training influences learner behavior and institutional practice.	percentage of learners reporting behavior change (e.g., more service users, less mistakes when doing tasks, etc.)

1.4 Develop scalability and sustainability strategies

Scaling a training programme within a research infrastructure such as OPERAS requires a strategic, collaborative, and modular approach that ensures quality, adaptability, but also sustainability. The primary goal of scalability is to reach more users, audiences, and contexts. In other words, it focuses on growth and expansion. Sustainability aims at maintaining long-term value, relevance, and functionality. It goes beyond just creating training materials. It is about maintaining, evolving, and embedding the programme into the broader ecosystem. While scalability and sustainability are closely related and often overlap, they focus on different goals, and therefore involve distinct actions and strategies.

This framework was built to allow scalability and sustainability of training programmes. This is possible because the framework enables standardisation as it provides a consistent methodology for how training content should be designed, developed and evaluated. However, the framework does not standardise the content.

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This ensures quality and coherence without imposing a one-size-fits-all solution.

The recommendation to use the FAIR-by-Design methodology also makes scalability and sustainability easier. This means using reusable **open formats** and making **training materials openly licensed** and storing them in a shared, accessible repositories or training catalogues, using appropriate metadata ensure easy discovery, reuse, and adaptation by others across the infrastructure and beyond.

Having feedback mechanisms and continuous improvement embedded in the framework facilitate metrics analysis and iterative inputs from the community. This makes a living training programme, able to evolve with trainers needs and to remain relevant over time. **Monitoring and evaluation** provide data to improve effectiveness and justify scaling and ensure sustainability by informing strategic improvements and aligning training with evolving needs.

Besides these embedded features of the framework, other actions can support scalability and sustainability. Modularizing content, breaking it into smaller, self-contained modules, allows different communities to mix and match what they need, enabling broader reuse and faster adaptation for various audiences, disciplines, or languages. In other words, a **modular design** fosters scalability by allowing training to be adapted and deployed in different contexts and by different institutions.

Keeping version-controlled documentation and providing clear update procedures, contributor guidelines, and changelogs contribute to a sustainable evolution of the programme. It also reduces development time for new training, lowering long-term resource needs.

The **translation and contextualization** of training materials for local needs and languages is also a way to scale training to different communities and to ensure local relevance and cultural inclusivity over time, especially non-English speaking communities. It also supports sustainability by increasing relevance and reuse, attracting continued support.

Developing a **Train of Trainers model** is a way to identify and support local or institutional champions or advocates who can deliver training within their contexts (their institution or National Node for example). This type of model can provide such champions or advocates with facilitator guides, presentation kits, and evaluation tools so they can confidently deliver sessions and scale the reach without needing central coordination every time. A sustainable training programme relies on a distributed network of contributors—trainers, developers, librarians, and support staff—who co-create, deliver, and maintain content.

Scalability and sustainability also depend on technology, community and funding. **Technical and technological infrastructures** ensure reliable delivery of training over time and across platforms and formats. **Collaborative partnerships and community engagement** enables shared development, maintenance burdens, and fosters ongoing engagement. **Funding and internal resources** allow the carry out of activities such as translations, platform updates, etc. and provide continuity and accountability.

When developing a training programme, it is important to map which actions to support scalability and sustainability are already embedded. Table 6 presents a summary of actions to be considered for different areas. Strategies that strengthen both dimensions should be prioritised, especially when resources are scarce. Different team members and partners can take on different roles to share the effort of scaling and sustaining a training programme.

Table 6. Strategic actions to support scalability and sustainability

Strategic Area	Action for scalability	Action for sustainability	Overlapping action
Reusable Content Formats and Licensing	Release materials under open licenses (e.g., CC BY)	Host in trusted, persistent repositories (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub)	Ensure open access with persistent identifiers and good metadata
Monitoring and Evaluation	Gather feedback during rapid roll-out in new contexts	Use feedback loops to improve and adapt content regularly	Set up lightweight metrics and reporting to track quality and use
Modular Design	Develop modular, customizable training units	Maintain a clear update/versioning process	Use open, well-documented templates to ensure reusability
Localization, Multilingual Support, and Inclusion	Translate and adapt content to different languages and contexts	Develop workflows for regular updates and local customization	Partner with National Nodes and local institutions to co-maintain translations
Training delivery and Train of trainers programme	Implement a train of trainer approach for broader reach	Support a community of trainers with ongoing mentorship and resources	Build regional and national trainer networks with shared materials
Technical /Technological Infrastructure	Use scalable, open platforms (e.g., Moodle, GitBook, GitHub)	Plan for long-term platform maintenance, data backup, and tech support	Choose platforms that support both wide access and longevity

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Collaborative Partnerships and Community Engagement	Reach out to new user groups and nodes through outreach and events	Foster a community of practice that co-creates and stewards materials	Incentivize participation (e.g., recognition, co-authorship)
Funding and Resources (core funding, in-kind staff time, or integration into funded projects)	Seek short-term grants or project funding to scale fast	Make the value of training visible to funders and leadership by tracking impact.	Embed training costs in project proposals, service budgets, or institutional support programmes.

Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined a comprehensive framework for the development, delivery, and evaluation of training in Open Science and open scholarly communication within the OPERAS infrastructure. The framework consolidates existing practices and introduces a structured methodology—anchored in the ADDIE model for instructional design, FAIR-by-Design principles, and Open Educational Resource standards—that ensures methodological rigour, inclusivity, and long-term sustainability.

Training is positioned as a strategic enabler for OPERAS, directly contributing to the achievement of its mission and to its transition toward European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) status. It supports the effectiveness of OPERAS services, reinforces the capacity of National Nodes, and underpins community-wide adoption of Open Science practices, especially in scholarly communication. By establishing a coherent, adaptable, and scalable approach, the framework responds to the identified need for consistency across training initiatives while accommodating the diversity inherent to the federated and multilingual character of the OPERAS community.

The production of a modular toolkit provides a practical instrument for implementing training programmes across a wide range of contexts and target groups. It facilitates interoperability, reusability, and alignment with European and international policy priorities on Open Science, while enabling multilingualism and local adaptations.

The framework provides a structured pathway for developing effective service end-user training programmes within OPERAS. It guides through the full cycle of training design and delivery: assessing whether training is necessary, defining the target audience and their needs, setting learning outcomes, selecting appropriate methods, and developing FAIR-compliant training material. Once implemented,

training programmes must be evaluated through feedback and performance metrics to ensure relevance, effectiveness, and continuous improvement.

The future implementation of this framework will require sustained efforts in three interrelated areas:

- Collaboration, ensuring inclusivity, co-ownership, and shared expertise co-ownership of training across OPERAS partners and alignment with other infrastructures and initiatives in the European Research Area (ERA);
- Monitoring, through systematic use of metrics and feedback mechanisms to gather provide evidence of training effectiveness and alignment with the infrastructure's goals, measure impact, identify gaps, and inform continuous improvement;
- Scalability and sustainability, by embedding open licensing, modular design, and FAIR-compliant practices, ensuring that training materials remain accessible, adaptable, and relevant over time. Sustainability is reinforced by continuous feedback, translation and local contextualisation, and Train-the-Trainer development, as well as reliable technical, community, and funding support.

In conclusion, this framework constitutes an essential component of OPERAS' strategic development. It not only strengthens the infrastructure's capacity to deliver high-quality training to its stakeholders but also contributes to advancing the broader objectives of the ERA by promoting openness, inclusivity, and excellence in scholarly communication across the Social Sciences and Humanities.

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Annexes

Annex 1 – Learning outcomes for a ToT on Open Science, RDM and FAIR Principles²⁴

Module Title	Topics	Learning outcomes
Module 1- Planning: research in the SSH OS landscape	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Introduction to the core principles of Open Science ● Exploration of key discussion points specific to the SSH ● Reflection on SSH's role within the broader Open Science movement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define Open Science and its various concepts ● Recognise Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) specificities across the research lifecycle, including practices and types of data, in the context of Open Science
Module 2- Data in the SSH: Standards, Principles and Practices for Research Data Management (RDM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding the fundamentals of research data management ● Introduction to the FAIR and CARE Principles ● Importance and structure of Data Management Plans (DMPs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Summarise research data management practices and requirements, with a focus on SSH specificities. ● Describe FAIR (and CARE) principles and how they improve data management. ● Identify the structural components of a Data Management Plan and its purpose within a research project.
Module 3- Dissemination of research: share and publish your research with OS Principles in mind	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focus on sharing research outputs in line with Open Science practices ● Guidance on what types of outputs to disseminate ● Considerations for long-term preservation and accessibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Explain how publishing diverse research outputs enhances transparency in research. ● Identify where and how to disseminate outputs for reuse across disciplines and communities. ● Choose appropriate tools, licenses, and repositories to maximise impact and long-term accessibility.

²⁴The whole training is available here: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=94>

<p>Module 4- Research framework: policy, funding and societal value of OS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview of the current Open Science policy environment, and how it influences practices and funding ● Understand differentiation of national policy landscapes ● Explore the links with Citizen Science and trends and future directions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Describe the current Open Science policy environment and how it influences SSH research practices and funding. ● Compare national Open Science policy landscapes and recognise key differences. ● Identify examples of Citizen Science in SSH and discuss their role in enhancing the societal impact of Open Science.
<p>Module 5 - Guidelines for trainers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation of backwards design method and its phases ● Definition of learning objectives with its types and characteristics ● Global presentation of types of assessment ● Global presentation of types of learning experience including passive and active learning ● Considerations about aligning the constituents of training plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define backward design and its steps ● Write effective learning objectives ● Choose the appropriate types of assessment ● Choose the appropriate learning experience ● Align the design elements

Annex 2 – Learning outcomes on diamond OA publishing for scholarly communication professionals²⁵

Categories	Title	Learning outcomes
Funding, sustainability and governance	Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore funding sources that align with Diamond Open Access principles • Discover common funding challenges and practical solutions • Explore strategies to maintain editorial independence while ensuring financial sustainability
	Ownership and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How Diamond Open Access core principles guide publisher's governance and ownership practices • How to apply these principles across all operational levels, from institutional relationships to editorial workflows • Key steps involved during the transition process
Editorial Management	Editorial quality and management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to improve a journal's peer review process. • What main editorial information should be displayed on a journal's website
	Open peer review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The different aspects of peer review that can be opened – e.g. identities, reports, participation, etc. • How each open peer review model creates specific opportunities and challenges for editors, reviewers, and authors. • Key considerations to evaluate which open peer review approach best fits your specific needs.
	Research integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key research integrity concepts and principles. • How to develop and implement effective research integrity policies. • Strategies for addressing and managing research integrity concerns.
Legal and ethical issues	Open policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why sharing this information is so important to advance research. • How to encourage researchers to adopt open sharing practices. • Key considerations when writing a data sharing policy.

²⁵ The whole training is available here: <https://training.diamas.org>

	Copyright and licenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to select appropriate open licenses that maximise research impact • How to develop and communicate transparent policies that both protect scholarly work and promote open knowledge sharing • Practical approaches for addressing third-party content and implementing best practices for license display
	Equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How discrimination and exclusion can occur in scholarly publishing • What EDIB means and why it matters • How to implement EDIB practices in your organisation, focusing on gender diversity, multilingualism, accessibility, and inclusive language
Technical aspects	Digital preservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to prepare your content for archiving using recommended formats and metadata. • What tools and services can help preserve your journal, even with a small budget. • How to make your content accessible and discoverable over time.
	Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why proper metadata is essential for indexing and long-term accessibility • How to apply best practices for curating and displaying metadata • What metadata elements and standards support discoverability and interoperability
	Choosing a software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to assess your publishing needs and workflows. • What to look for in platform features and hosting models. • How to align your platform choice with Diamond OA values and standards.
	Preprints and repositories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How preprints and repositories can complement formal journal publishing • How to encourage and guide authors on using repositories and preprints effectively. • How to integrate repository deposits into your publishing workflow

Promotion,
dissemination
and indexing

Visibility,
discoverability and
impact

- Ensure a journal and its content are easily discoverable online through transparent policies, indexing strategies and technical considerations
- Develop targeted communication strategies and a strong visual identity to engage your scholarly community effectively.
- Apply various metrics and analytical tools to track usage, measure effectiveness, and responsibly evaluate publication impact.

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Annex 3: Potential target learners for the different training programmes

Topic	Target learner	
OS/RDM/FAIR ²⁶	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SSH researchers at any career stage aiming to further develop their knowledge on the topics and who need to develop skills to guide and support other SSH researchers in employing OS sciences. ● Research support staff (such as librarians) looking for new skills to train SSH researchers and PhD students to employ OS practices. ● Some basic knowledge of the topics is necessary in case of a ToT. 	
Diamond OA ²⁷	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Directors and managers of publishing services (e.g., university presses, OA journal publishers, and editorial boards) who need guidance on flipping journals to Diamond OA, setting up new journals, and implementing best practices. ● Publishing professionals, such as copy editors, proof-readers, and other implementers who need practical training on editorial workflows and technical processes. ● Regional, national, or international publishing infrastructure providers (journal hosting services and data centres) seeking to support institutional publishers with documentation and training content. ● Standard & best practice providers who both inform and implement quality standards, and seek to provide practical guidance on how institutional publishers can meet current standards and best practices. For instance, organisations like DOAJ, Sherpa Romeo, and Crossref. 	
Service end-users ²⁸	GoTriple	SSH researchers; authors, editors; editorial managers; publishers; libraries; translators
	PRISM	SSH researchers; authors; publishers; libraries

²⁶ Based on Skills4EOSC Train of Trainers

²⁷ Based on DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA training

²⁸ Based on the framework for user-centred quality on selected services (Pehar, F., & Pavlović, N. P., 2023)

	Hypotheses	SSH researchers; authors; publishers; libraries
	OPERAS Metrics	SSH researchers; publishers; libraries
	VERA	SSH researchers; publishers; libraries
	Pathfinder	Authors; publishers; editors; editorial managers
	Mondaecus	Translators, authors, editors

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Annex 4: Template of the Framework article

Article Title

Summary

Up to 50 words

Main text

Up to 1000 words

Related articles

Link to related articles

Templates

Link to the templates in case there is any.

References

What is cited in the text (including images used, if it's the case).

Further reading

Reference to complementary sources if it's the case.

Keywords

Keywords are an integral part of the article. They can appear in the Glossary.

Authors

Name (ORCID)

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Annex 5: Training toolkit

Articles

Framework Category	Article Title
Analysis	Types of analysis
	Needs analysis
	Data sources
	Learner's analysis
	Task analysis
Design	Learning outcomes
	Effective Learning outcomes
	Learning objectives or learning outcomes
	Assessment methods
	Learning experience
	Alignment and blueprint
	Backward design
	FAIR-By-Design methodology
Development	Training development
Implementation	Training implementation
Evaluation	Evaluation
	Designing evaluation questions

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Types of analysis

Summary

- Four types of analysis can be carried out before designing and delivering training.
 - Needs analysis
 - Job-Task analysis
 - Learners' analysis
 - Contextual analysis

Main text

Analyzing before designing and delivering training is often neglected. However, thorough analysis leads to identifying the causes of the issues to be addressed, understanding learners' needs, and taking into consideration the different aspects (including constraints and advantages) of a given context. Four types of analysis can be carried out to help answer different questions.

Needs analysis is important when there is a desire for change. Such change can be related to knowledge, attitude, or behavior. This type of analysis highlights the reasons for the change and how it can be achieved. It can be done more formally through data collection and analysis, or informally when the information already exists. This type of analysis establishes if training is necessary.

Job-task analysis is conducted after the training need has been identified. This is where you analyze the tasks that must be performed to complete a job, as well as the frequency, level of difficulty, and importance of each task. The

resulting information can be used to design practice activities that address the highest priority behaviors.

Learners' analysis reveals who the potential learners are and what characteristics they present. It highlights the new behaviors to be developed and the existing learning constraints. Finally, it points to pedagogical considerations and modes of delivery. Skipping this analysis risks frustrating the trainees and adding unnecessary friction to the learning process.

Contextual analysis focuses on the instructional context the learners will be in when they interact with training. It is not the most common type of analysis, but it is important because it helps to eliminate barriers to learning such as time or technological constraints. In other words, it is useful to identify for example if the instruction will be face-to-face or if it will be eLearning. It points to which tools and technologies will be necessary during the training. Analyzing the instructional context before designing any training facilitates its tailor while taking into account any potential limitations.

Related articles

Needs analysis

Task analysis

Learners' analysis

Templates

Perform needs analysis

Further reading

Conklin, S., Oyarzun, B., Reese, R. M., & Stefaniak, J. E. (2021). A Practitioner's Guide to Instructional Design in Higher Education.

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Watkins, R., West Meiers, M., & Visser, Y. (2012). *A Guide to Assessing Needs: Essential Tools for Collecting Information, Making Decisions, and Achieving Development Results*. The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-0-8213-8868-6>

Keywords

analysis, training design

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Needs analysis

Summary

- Problem and/or opportunity are typically identified through needs analysis.
- The needs lie between the current and desired performance levels.
- Training is not always the answer.
- Steps of needs analysis:
 - Identify the problem/opportunity
 - Identify the types of data
 - Collect data
 - Analyse data
 - Prepare recommendations

Main text

Before implementing training activities, it is crucial to identify the training needs, i.e., problems to be solved, or opportunities to be seized through training. Needs analysis is what enables such identification.

Needs analysis aims to identify existing gaps in performance or areas for improvement. The needs lie between the current and desired performance levels. This type of analysis guides the establishment of priorities and the evaluation of the costs of filling (or not) such gaps.

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Despite being complex and time-consuming, gathering appropriate and sufficient information to guide the training design process is crucial to effectively address the needs, including assessing whether the results should be achieved through the implementation of non-training or training interventions.

➔ Training is not always the answer!

After identifying the training intervention as necessary, the needs analysis takes a step further and uncovers the underlying factors contributing to the performance gaps. In simple terms, it is time to identify the “what”, “who”, “where”, “when”, and “why” for the gaps. Identifying the elements that support or hinder the situation leads to the development of sustainable solutions to close the performance gap.

Needs analysis steps

The needs analysis process includes five steps: identifying a problem, identifying data sources, collecting data, analyzing data, and making recommendations (Adapted from Conklin et al., 2021).

1. Problem identification

This step is usually carried out when training is brought to the table. It could happen, for instance, in the context of a funded project or when a new service is developed.

This step helps identify whether the problem can be solved or an opportunity can be seized through training.

2. Data sources identification

This step provides a deeper understanding of the situation. Collecting data that offers insights from various perspectives is beneficial for a more comprehensive analysis. Potential data sources include, among other things, task analyses, direct observations, focus groups, interviews, document reviews, evaluations of existing work products, and surveys.

This step helps to identify the current state and the desired state of affairs.

3. Data collection

In this step, data is collected according to the sources identified previously. The collection should provide answers to two relevant questions.

A. Why aren't people performing as they should?

This question helps identify the causes of the performance gap. The issues can be environmental, such as lack of material or technology, insufficient incentives, or cultural environment. The root cause could also be a lack of knowledge or skills. For example:

Why publication managers aren't applying metadata properly?

Why aren't there more users for this discovery service?

Why aren't researchers doing a data management plan?

➔ A knowledge or skill gap can be addressed through training.

B. What will help people perform better?

This question helps to identify how to eliminate the barriers. In the case of environmental issues, the answer could be to update technology or offer more incentives. When the barriers are caused by a lack of knowledge or skills, the strategy would rather involve exposing people to new concepts and providing them opportunities to practice.

4. Data analysis

Through this step, it is possible to identify patterns and key factors influencing the initial problem. The insights gained from the data collection and analysis allow for reformulating the problem to better reflect the actual situation.

5. Recommendations

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The final step consists of compiling a list of recommendations for training. These suggestions are often ranked based on the priorities of the organization, group of stakeholders, or community. The feasibility of developing training, costs, and staff availability can also feed the priority analysis.

Related articles

Data sources

Templates

Perform needs analysis

References

Conklin, S., Oyarzun, B., Reese, R. M., & Stefaniak, J. E. (2021). *A Practitioner's Guide to Instructional Design in Higher Education*.

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Watkins, R., West Meiers, M., & Visser, Y. (2012). *A Guide to Assessing Needs: Essential Tools for Collecting Information, Making Decisions, and Achieving Development Results*. The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-0-8213-8868-6>

Keywords

needs analysis

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Data Sources for Needs Analysis

Summary

Needs are usually defined as performance gaps.

Discrepancy perspective: process for identifying and measuring differences and inconsistencies between what is and what should be at the strategic, tactical, or operational level.

Appreciative inquiry perspective: a process that identifies and highlights the positive achievements, adding valuable information about what is working well and how one can build on those results.

Elements to be taken into account during the identification of data sources: people, methods, follow-up questions, and alignment between needs and constraints.

Examples of methods: interview, survey, focus groups, document analysis.

Main text

Data collection from multiple sources is crucial for designing training in an informed way because it takes into account the current and the desired state of affairs. Some types of data sources can inform the decision-making process during a needs assessment.

Watkins et al. (2012) state that needs are usually defined as performance gaps, and a discrepancy perspective of data and information is most typically associated with a needs analysis.

A discrepancy perspective views needs assessment as a process for identifying and measuring differences and inconsistency between what is and what

should be at the strategic, tactical, or operational level. Some examples of discrepancy are not enough adoption of Open Science Practices, resistance to publish in Open Access, low number of Open Science service users, lack of compliance with standards and requirements in publishing, etc.

In the appreciative inquiry perspective, on the other hand, needs assessment is a process that identifies and highlights the positive achievements, adding valuable information about what is working well and how one can build on those results.

Both perspectives used together can offer a more balanced view of performance. Survey data, interview responses, focus group results, performance observations, and document reviews are examples of needs assessment tools and techniques that can be used in both cases.

The following elements should be taken into account during the identification of the most appropriate and most effective data sources:

1. **Identify appropriate people.** Be sure to identify individuals within your organization or stakeholder groups who are familiar with the project or service, who care about it, and have the ability or authority to implement any changes that may result from the needs analysis.

Some examples of stakeholders groups in the context of open scholarly communication for the Social Sciences and Humanities can be:

- Authors
- Editors
- Editorial managers
- Librarians
- Publishers
- Translators
- SSH researchers
- Service providers
- Policy makers

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- Other

2. **Identify the appropriate methods.** Considering the goals of the training project, time and budget constraints, and the stakeholders to be consulted, the methods to collect data will be identified. A survey allows for gathering much more data than focus groups, and reviewing documents give different insights than directly observing practices.

3. **Always ask “WHY?”.** When conducting a needs analysis, asking follow-up questions to help to understand *why* a situation is occurring or what is causing a specific issue. Asking *why* is a tool to mitigate uncertainty.

4. **Align needs analysis activities with the constraints of a given training project.** Every project comes with constraints. It is okay to scale the needs analysis activities based upon the time constraints or resources associated with a project. A needs analysis to improve an existing training can be quite different from one aiming at developing a new programme.

Methods

1. Interviews

Individual interviews can be conducted with different stakeholders. Interviews allow gathering information on a more detailed level from individual perspectives. You can use:

- Interviews with researchers at different career levels to identify the knowledge they need to develop and the skills they need to acquire.
- Interviews with service users to understand the kind of support they need to make better use of a given service.
- Interview with trainers to identify the gaps in existing training.

2. Focus groups

A focus group method uses a small sample of the target group and it provides a forum for open discussion about a selected topic. Discussions should be led by a skilled moderator. It is an effective method to explore complex issues.

- Focus groups can be conducted with 5-8 individuals at a time.

- Focus groups with service providers to identify training needs regarding a service.
- Focus groups with scholarly communication professionals to identify needs regarding their editorial management practices.

3. Surveys

Surveys are a useful tool to collect information from a large group of stakeholders. It allows gathering of demographic data, preferences, attitudes, opinions, etc., and it is flexible and customizable, providing vast information on different topics.

- Survey with researchers used to assess researchers' current and missing skills, identifies unmet training needs and challenges in accessing online learning resources in the ATRIUM²⁹ project (Delmazo et al, 2025).
- Survey was used to describe the landscape of institutional publishing in Europe carried out in the context of the DIAMAS³⁰ project. It provides a good overview of areas that need attention and issues that need further investigation (Armengou et al. 2023).

4. Gap analysis

Finally, needs analysis is also known as gap analysis. Here are some examples of gap analysis carried out in the context of funded projects. Such documents can be an important source of information to design training for the target stakeholders.

- The technical gap analysis within CRAFT-OA³¹ reveals gaps ranging from insufficient application of technical standards to challenges related to publishing software, and proposes solutions to them including training.

²⁹ ATRIUM: European Commission funded project aiming at improving access to leading research infrastructures in the Arts and Humanities by enhancing the quality of metadata in existing catalogues and repositories (<https://atrium-research.eu/>).

³⁰ DIAMAS: European Commission funded project that aims at delivering an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable institutional OA scholarly publication ecosystem for the ERA (<https://diamasproject.eu/>).

³¹ CRAFT-OA: European Commission funded project focusing on improving the technical and organisational infrastructure of Diamond OA (<https://www.craft-oa.eu/>).

- Gap analysis, assessing the alignment of Open Access Diamond Journals (OADJs) with recommended technical best practices outlined in a previous report on standards for best publishing practices and basic technical requirements in the light of FAIR principles (Laakso et al., 2023). This gap analysis was also carried out by the CRAFT-OA project.

5. Document analysis

Documents can be a rich source of information. Reports, survey analysis carried out in projects, curriculums, etc. can provide different types of information.

- Identify and list roles and responsibilities of the job in which training will be provided.
 - Minimum Viable Skillsets: a Briefing for Competence Centres (White, A., & Green, D.,2025).
- Review the skills, knowledge and attitude required in order to successfully perform the job.
 - Minimum Viable Skillsets: a Briefing for Competence Centres (White, A., & Green, D.,2025).
 - Reusable curriculum for upskilling training, CRAFT-OA Project (Kupreyev et al., 2024).

Evaluation of existing training gathered through feedback forms, interviews or any other method is also a source of information for the decision regarding the development of new training or the improvement of existing ones.

Related articles

Needs analysis

Job-task analysis

Learners' analysis

Templates

Perform needs analysis

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Keywords

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needs analysis methods, gap analysis

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Tasks analysis

Summary

After conducting a needs analysis, task analysis systematically breaks down tasks into steps to develop targeted instruction. It helps instructional designers create relevant, efficient training by understanding task components, prior knowledge, and performance standards, ultimately ensuring learning aligns with real-world requirements and improves learner skill acquisition.

Main text

After a needs analysis is conducted, it is necessary to conduct a task analysis. Task analysis is the process of breaking down tasks and activities into a series of steps to understand how they are performed (Raible, 2020). Task analysis enables instructional designers to create focused and effective learning experiences by understanding the detailed components involved in performing specific tasks. It usually includes: task descriptions, subordinate tasks, importance of tasks, length and frequency of tasks, task difficulty, equipment required to do the task, and the work environment and conditions in which the task is performed (McDonald and West, 2021).

When design training, task analysis is useful because it helps to:

- establish precise and measurable learning outcomes, once the specific tasks learners must perform are identified.

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- design effective assessments that accurately measure learners' proficiency in performing those tasks.
- ensure the relevance of the training content which will focus on the skills and knowledge that are directly applicable to the task at hand.
- customize training delivery as training can be tailored to the learners' needs, ensuring greater engagement and retention.

Different types of tasks warrant different forms of task analyses as well as different forms of data collection to inform analysis. Such variety can represent a challenge in establishing best practices.

Task analysis steps

1. Identify the overall task or goal that learners need to accomplish. This could be anything from creating a profile in a service, applying metadata to a paper in a digital journal or employing best practices related to the use of AI tools in the scholarly communication environment. The key is to understand the big picture. For instance, if you're designing training for data providers, the overall task might be "provide content to a discovery platform".

2. Break the task into smaller sub-tasks or actions that make up the process. These sub-tasks should be the individual steps needed to complete the task successfully. If the task is to "provide content to a discovery platform", the sub-tasks could be "verify compliance with technical requirements of the platform", "adapt or modify technical aspects to comply with such requirements" or "set up a data repository in the service platform".

3. Define the skills and knowledge required for each sub-task. Does the learner need specific technical knowledge? Are there critical decision-making points? For instance, when setting up a data repository in in a platform, the learner might need to deal with specific types of metadata

4. Determine the sequence of sub-tasks and verify if the order might have an impact on the result. For example, "verify compliance with requirements must

happen before the “set-up of a data repository”. It can also be necessary to verify if the task and subtasks are frequently performed and if there are conditions and constraints that could impact the way they are performed. These might include environmental factors, time limitations, or system restrictions.

Once the tasks are analysed, the following steps consist of determining if prior knowledge to perform the task is necessary, developing learning outcomes for each task, deciding on the assessment method and designing the activities for each performed task.

Task analysis offers, thus, a structured approach to breaking down tasks into manageable components. Understanding the skills, knowledge, and sequence required to complete a task allows for the creation of more effective, focused, and engaging training experiences.

Related articles

Needs analysis

Learner’s analysis

Data sources

Template

Task analysis

References

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Keywords

task analysis, real-world needs, needs analysis

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Learners' analysis

Summary

Learner analysis is the process of gathering and interpreting information about learners to inform the instructional design and to produce learner-centred training. Key categories of learner characteristics include: demographic, entry-level competencies, and personal or social factors. These categories provide the information to describe user groups or create personas. Data can be collected through varied ways but special emphasis is placed on open consultation with communities, recognizing the importance of participatory approaches in identifying training priorities and barriers.

Main text

Learner analysis is the process of gathering and interpreting information about learners to inform the instructional design of training programs. It forms a crucial part of the needs analysis phase and represents a systematic approach to understanding the training audience. Effective training is fundamentally learner-centered, and therefore, understanding who the learners are is essential for developing meaningful, relevant, and accessible learning experiences.

➔ *Effective training is fundamentally learner-centered!*

The primary objective of this phase is to identify and define the target user group(s) for training, enabling the preparation of appropriate methodologies,

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content, and materials. These can be considered as different **user groups**, matching learners with similar characteristics into one group for training. It is also possible to build **proto personas**, based on the data collected from surveys, interviews etc., that can tell us more about the fictional user representing each group.

Three main categories of learner characteristics need to be considered: general or demographic characteristics, specific entry characteristics (prerequisite skills for the instruction), and personal or social characteristics. Additional crucial characteristics include academic information, personal and social characteristics, culturally diverse learners, learners with disabilities, and adult learners.

1. General or demographic characteristics include variables such as gender distribution, age range, and ethnicity. It can also include previous work experience and nature and range of educational background. Such characteristics have an impact on training approaches.

For example, what would be a good approach if the participants are potential service users in the beginning of their academic education? What if the learners are senior researchers?

2. Specific entry characteristics or competencies refer to skills and attitudes that learners need to demonstrate to benefit from the training. Analysis of such competences is fundamental before the design of instruction because it determines the entry characteristics of typical target trainees.

For example, in the case of a Train of Trainers programme on Open Science and Research Data Management, it is helpful to know if most trainees have extensive experience related to the course topic. Knowing the trainee's knowledge and skills is very important in determining the appropriate entry level and establishing pre-requisites for the instruction.

The second aspect regards trainees' attitude toward course content, potential delivery system or training organization. Learner centered training focuses on content that is significant for the trainees and happens in a welcoming environment.

3. Personal and social characteristics such as motivation expectations and vocational aspiration, need of rewards, bias, prejudice and beliefs, general learning experiences, and previous or current employment and work experiences can also help to plan the training.

For example, is training important for career advancement? Are the learners interested in acquiring knowledge or do they need a certificate?

Additional learner characteristics can be considered:

- Digital literacy
- Access to technology and training platforms
- Cultural context and linguistic diversity
- Learning barriers, including disabilities

Learners' characteristics can be used to describe profiles or create personas.

User groups profiles

User group profiles are “generalised descriptions of specific user segments, highlighting their shared characteristics and contexts of use” (Pehar, F., & Pavlović, N. P., 2023).

For each user groups profiles, it is essential to define:

- Main goals
- Prior knowledge and training
- Skills (Digital literacy, use of technology etc.)
- Learning needs
- Constraints and problems

For example, in a user group made of *SSH early career researchers*, one could imagine the following profile:

- Main goals:
 - *To learn about how to choose a credible open access journal*
- Prior knowledge and training:
 - *Familiar with academic norms and requirements*
 - *Knows a little about open science platforms and practices, FAIR data, and use of open repositories and open learning materials*
- Skills (Digital literacy, use of technology etc.):

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- *Advanced user*
- Learning needs:
 - *Practical understanding of open access publishing options and different platforms*
- Constraints and problems
 - *Uncertainty about institutional support and use of open access platforms and journals*

Personas

Personas are “detailed descriptions of fictitious yet realistic” learners aiming at promoting “empathy among designers, empowering them to understand user needs, motivations, and behaviours and effectively address them (Pehar, F., & Pavlović, N. P., 2023). It is based on research, data and/or insights about the training audience and is useful in guiding design decisions, for instance, content, technology, delivery methods, activities, and assessments.

A persona template should describe some characteristics, such as:

- Name
- Age
- Role
- Background
- Prior knowledge
- Pain points

Data Collection Methods

Describing learners’ profile or creating learners’ personas depends on a thorough audience analysis, which involves conducting surveys and interviews with representative audience members, along with other stakeholders involved in the learning process. Also access to data, such as career progression, demographics, past job positions, and related details can be useful. Carefully reviewing and analyzing this information is key to creating personas that accurately represent the real audience, rather than simply reflecting general assumptions. Some methods to collect the data are:

- Surveys
- Interviews and focus groups

- Learning analytics from past programs
- Informal consultations or pilot testing

Participatory training approach: open consultation

Beyond traditional data collection methods (e.g., interviews, questionnaires, surveys), open access training projects benefit greatly from open community consultation. Involving potential learners and stakeholders in the planning process ensures that training is not only designed *for* them but also *with* them. Community engagement can uncover learner needs, and validate content relevance.

Consultation strategies may include:

- Co-design workshops
- Open calls for feedback on training materials
- Advisory panels or working groups representing different learner types
- Iterative prototyping of learning materials with community input

Conclusion

By recognizing and analyzing learners' various characteristics, training designers can better align instructional strategies with learner needs and expectations, with a main goal to improve the learning outcomes. Learners' analysis answers the question of who the learner is. Identifying the learner also highlights aspects such as existing learning opportunities and constraints, as well as pedagogical considerations.

Related articles

Needs analysis

Task analysis

Data sources

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Template

Learner's analysis

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Pehar, F., & Pavlović, N. P. (2023). Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 6.1) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081977>

Further reading

[How to complete a Learner Analysis and Persona: A Deep Dive into Understanding Your Audience](#)

[Digital learning toolkit](#)

Keywords

learner-centered, learners analysis, user profile, persona

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FAIR-By-Design Methodology

Summary

The Skills4EOSC project developed a FAIR-by-design methodology to guide the creation of FAIR learning materials. By integrating best practices and a six-stage workflow, it enhances accessibility, sustainability, and quality in education. This approach empowers educators to produce reusable, interoperable content that supports lifelong learning and fosters a collaborative teaching ecosystem.

Main text

What is the FAIR-by-design methodology

The Skills4EOSC³² project developed a comprehensive FAIR-by-design methodology that covers all aspects of the process of developing FAIR learning materials. Building on previous work done in other EOSC projects, while incorporating best practices from related activities (e.g., implementation of learning platforms, development of self-paced courses, definitions of metadata schemas for training materials and integration of training catalogues), this methodology is now a tool that can be used by the community of training/learning materials designers. It represents an important step in upskilling their traditional design process by offering the means to ensure FAIRness of the produced learning content (FILIPOSKA, Sonja, et al., 2003a).

Making learning materials FAIR adds a considerable overhead on the already lengthy process of developing new learning resources. However, focusing on the development of FAIR learning materials presents many benefits including:

³² Skills4eosc <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>

- Expanded base of learners: FAIR materials support lifelong learning by being accessible to anyone, not just targeted groups (such as OS practitioners).
- Improved learning process: Learners can easily find, access, and revisit content, enhancing understanding and flexibility.
- High-quality learning materials: Materials can be updated, adapted, translated and localized more easily, supported by clear metadata and licensing.
- Sustainable education: FAIR practices contribute to a more sustainable educational ecosystem by reducing redundancy, maximizing resource utilization, and embracing openness to support the efficient use of educational resources.
- Scalability and efficiency: FAIR materials can be easily distributed and shared, fostering a more efficient and scalable education system.
- Consolidated network of instructors: FAIR materials enable collaborative development and review by educators.

Steps of the FAIR-by-design methodology

The necessary steps to ensure the production of FAIR-by-design learning materials are outlined in a six-stage workflow that extends the traditional instructional design process with additional activities aiming to through the incorporation of the FAIR principles. Each stage of the workflow presents the relevant aspects of learning material development blending learning models, materials and methods with the FAIR requirements. The 6 main steps are iteratively repeated within a continuous improvement loop.

1. Prepare

- develop FAIR skills that will augment the traditional instructional design skills. These include FAIR principles, Intellectual Property Rights, licensing, attribution, permanent identifiers (PIDs) and metadata
- define the purpose, learning objectives and audience targets

2. Discover

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- identify existing learning materials
- assess the potential for their reuse

3. Design

- define the syllabus and create the learning materials structure
- start a facilitators guide
- ensure interoperability by choosing open licenses

4. Produce

- use open authoring tools and formats
- develop accessible content
- define metadata

5. Publish

- deposit the learning content for learners and for instructors
- use PIDs
- define access rights and provide attribution guidelines
- enable feedback gathering
- list in relevant catalogues

6. Verify

- go through a quality assurance (QA) process to verify FAIRness

Related articles

backward design

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Further reading

Interactive map with an overview of the steps of the FAIR-by-design methodology:

https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/FAIR-by-Design_Book/imagemap/

FAIR-by-Design Methodology for Learning Materials Training of Trainers:

https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/FAIR-by-Design_ToT/latest/

FAIR-by-design

microlearning:

<https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/microlearning/latest/>

Keywords

FAIR-by-design, Skills4EOSC, FAIR principles, learning materials

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Backwards Design

Summary

Backward design is an instructional design method that begins with identifying the desired learning outcomes that learners should accomplish at the end of the training. It has three steps that should be aligned:

- identification of learning outcomes
- selecting the type of assessment evidence and
- planning the learning experiences.

Main text

Backward design is an instructional planning method that begins with identifying the desired learning outcomes for learners at the end of the course, instead of merely focusing on the content and topics to be covered. This process has proven to be an effective tool for creating instructional contexts, whether for single sessions, tutorials, or complete semester-length courses.

After identifying the outcomes, one works backwards to design course components that align with these outcomes and support the teaching objectives. Such an approach ensures that educational activities and assessments align with and support the achievement of the established goals. In other words, it ensures that what has been taught and measured are indeed the learning outcomes established.

Advantages of the backward design method

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The backward design method is consistent with a learner-centred approach to training, focusing on learning outcomes and engaging learners in their learning. Such active learning facilitates connecting theory and practice and constructing new knowledge based on prior knowledge and experiences.

It also addresses the recurrent problems of treating textbooks and training material as the curriculum rather than resources, and having activity-oriented practices with no clear priorities and purposes.

Moreover, the method of backward design clarifies the rationale that lies behind the design. Doing so ensures that the planned activities effectively support learning outcomes, pointing out potential gaps or redundancies in the lesson plan.

Steps

The backward design process involves three steps that progressively lead from broad to more detailed planning of learning activities and resources. This approach follows a three-step process (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005):

1. identifying the desired outcomes;
2. determining the assessment evidence;
3. planning the learning experiences and the instruction methods.

Identifying the desired outcomes

Designing training starts by seeing the big picture, i.e., by identifying its objectives or outcomes. A few questions can help to find what the end goal is.

- What should learners know at the end of the training?
- What should they be able to do?

At this stage one can take into consideration goals of the curriculum, frameworks, results of gap analyses, etc., and keep focusing on the big ideas,

concepts, principles, theories, procedures and so on. The desired results will be the intended learning outcomes.

Determining assessment evidence

Once the desired results are identified, it is time to identify ways to verify what the learners know, that is, the “acceptable evidence” that such results were effectively obtained.

Backward design is a way to ensure the alignment between learning outcomes and assessment. The scope of the assessment should take into account the balance between knowledge and skills that are reflected in the learning outcomes.

The assessment can take the form of quizzes, projects, presentations, portfolios, and even tests. However, it is important to keep in mind that assessment does not mean grading. Grades, badges, certifications can be used as a proof of training, but here we are talking about the evidence we will collect for our assessment and how we will collect them throughout the training.

Planning the learning activities and instruction

Planning instructional activities aims to ensure that learners are taught the knowledge and skills they need to meet the established assessment criteria. At this stage, the most appropriate approach, method of content delivery, activities, and materials to be used are identified. The learning activities include lectures given or activities and practices used to facilitate learning.

Some questions can guide the process of identifying what constitutes the best instructional experience that will allow learners to achieve the desired results.

- What facts, concepts, principles, procedures and processes will learners need in order to achieve the end goals and to perform effectively?
- What kind of activity will best equip learners with knowledge and skills?
- What will need to be taught and how should it be taught?

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- What materials and resources are the most adequate to achieve this goal?

Conclusion

Two key takeaways are important when designing training. The first is that identifying and/or preparing the material, in whatever form (texts, books, slides, videos, etc.), is not a synonym for preparing and delivering training. The second is that assessment allows for verifying if objectives were accomplished; it is not the same as grading.

Related articles

Learning outcomes

Assessment

Learning Experience

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Keywords

backwards design, learning outcomes

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Learning outcomes

Summary

Learning outcomes (LO) are brief statements that describe the knowledge, skills or attitudes learners should be able to demonstrate by the end of a training programme, course or session. There are three types of learning outcomes: knowledge-based, skills-based and attitude-based.

Main text

Identifying the desired outcomes

The desired outcomes for the learners are directly connected to the needs in terms of knowledge, skills and competences they should acquire or develop. A needs analysis allows the identification of existing gaps in performance or areas for improvement. In other words, it helps to identify the current state and the desired state of affairs. Task analysis and learner's analysis also contribute to identifying the training needs.

Definition of Learning Outcomes

Learning outcomes (LO) are brief statements that describe the knowledge, skills or attitudes learners should be able to demonstrate by the end of a training programme, course or session.

Developing learning outcomes helps trainers to think about course content and its potential applications, focusing on the knowledge and skills that will be

most valuable for trainees. It also assists in the identification of the most useful methods of assessment and the most appropriate types of learning experience.

From a broader perspective, considering a particular course or unit within the context of a larger programme, developing learning outcomes contributes to the development of a more coherent curriculum and provides the structure to evaluate its efficiency, identify gaps and overlaps and clarify priorities.

From the trainees' perspective, learning outcomes help to understand why such knowledge and skills can be useful and what are the potential contexts of application. This understanding can lead to more engagement in the learning process. It also guides assessment and evaluation.

Types of learning outcomes

Learning outcomes describe the knowledge, skills and attitudes to be achieved by learners. In other words, these three areas point to the different aspects of learning that might take place in a training.

Knowledge-based outcomes describe the disciplinary information, measure the understanding of a concept. This type of content is usually fundamental for the development of future work during the training.

For example:

- *By the end of this course, learners will be able to cite UNESCO's principals for Open Science.*
- *The learner will be able to give the definition of a data management plan.*

Skill-based outcomes describe the learners' ability to perform tasks. This type of goal is used to assess the learner's ability to put their understanding of a concept into practice, to use the knowledge acquired to complete a given assignment.

For example:

- *By the end of this course, students will be able to employ the best*

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practices to store data securely and efficiently.

- *The learner will be able to efficiently do a data management plan.*

Attitude-based outcomes describe the values or beliefs imparted or investigated in a particular field or discipline. They are used to assess the learner’s attitude towards the concept or the skills learned. In other words, this type of objective is connected to the learner’s ability to think critically about a concept and their willingness to apply this knowledge in real-world situations. Attitude-oriented learning outcomes should focus on ways that the knowledge or skills developed during the training might impact the learner’s experiences throughout their research and work life.

For example:

- *By the end of this training, learners will be able to articulate the need of the research assessment reform to further develop OpenScience practices.*
- *The learner will be able to demonstrate the importance of doing a data management plan in the framework of open science.*

Related Framework articles

Effective Learning Outcomes

Learning objectives or learning outcomes?

Templates

Learning outcomes

References

Centre for Teaching Support & Innovation. “Course Design.” Accessed July 17, 2025. <https://teaching.utoronto.ca/resources/course-design/>.

Keywords

Learning outcomes

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Effective learning outcomes

Summary

Well-written learning outcomes are SMART: Specific, Measurable, Applicable, Realistic, and Time-bound. They clearly define expected skills and knowledge, use active future-tense verbs, avoid compound statements, and align with learners' abilities and course duration. The revised version of Bloom's Taxonomy supports verb selection, helping ensure objectives are assessable, engaging, and relevant for future application.

Main text

Characteristics of well-written learning outcomes

Effective learning outcomes are very specific and use active language, making that make expectations clear and ensuring that learners and instructor goals in the course are aligned (Centre for Teaching Support & Innovation).

➔ *Well written learning objectives are SMART.*

Learning objectives should be specific and well defined: explain in clear and concise terms the specific content, skills and attitudes learners should be able to demonstrate, produce, and know as a result of the course. This includes avoiding jargon and relying on active verbs in the future tense.

Learning objectives should be simple and not compound: avoid the use of bundled or compound statements that join the elements of two or more objectives into one statement. In case compound outcomes are necessary, it is important to avoid combining elements that cannot be assessed by a single method.

Learning objectives should be measurable: rely on the use of specific, active and observable verbs that demonstrate learning or a change in cognitive capacity. Using active verbs points to more effective ways to indicate how learning will be assessed. From the learners's perspective, well written learning outcomes prepare them for assessment and help them feel engaged in and empowered by the training process.

Learning objectives should be applicable: reflect and indicate the ways in which the learner is likely to use and integrate the acquired knowledge and skills in the future.

Learning objectives should be realistic: make sure that objectives are attainable. Objectives need to be reviewed in light of learners' ability, developmental levels, their initial skill sets, and the time available to attain these skill sets.

Learning objectives should be time-bound: offer a timeline by which the desired knowledge or skills should be acquired.

Bloom's taxonomy

Bloom's taxonomy³³ is a well-known framework to categorize educational objectives. Benjamin Bloom was responsible for leading the development of this framework in 1956. According to the taxonomy, learning outcomes should be divided into three broad domains: cognitive (knowledge-based), affective (emotion-based), and psychomotor (action-based). Each domain presents a hierarchy of skills and abilities. These domains are used by educators to structure curricula, assessments, and teaching methods to foster different types of learning, deeply entrenching the taxonomy in the learning and educational industries. The issue is that there is no cognitive research that

³³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bloom%27s_taxonomy

validates this hierarchy of thinking, but anyone involved with training design might come across Bloom’s taxonomy (Malamed, 2020)

There are newer versions of the original taxonomy that can be more appropriate. One example is Anderson and Krathwohl’s revision from 2001 (which is often seen as Bloom’s taxonomy revised).

Table 1. Anderson and Krathwohl’s Revised Taxonomy 2001 and Examples of action verbs to be used with each level.

Remember	
Definition	Examples of action verbs
Recognizing or recalling knowledge from memory. Remembering is when memory is used to produce or retrieve definitions, facts, or lists, or to recite previously learned information.	copy, define, describe, discover, duplicate, enumerate, find, identify, label, list, locate, match, memorize, name, omit, quote, recall, recognize, relate, reproduce, select, show, tabulate, tell
Understand	
Definition	Examples of action verbs
Constructing meaning from different types of functions be they written or graphic messages or activities like interpreting, exemplifying, classifying, summarizing, inferring, comparing, or explaining.	ask, classify, compare, contrast, demonstrate, describe, differentiate, discuss, distinguish, explain, express, extend, group, illustrate, infer, interpret, outline, paraphrase, relate, rephrase, restate, select, show, summarize, translate
Apply	
Definition	Examples of action verbs

<p>Carrying out or using a procedure through executing, or implementing. <i>Applying</i> relates to or refers to situations where learned material is used through products like models, presentations, interviews or simulations.</p>	<p>apply, build, calculate, construct, determine, develop, experiment with, identify, illustrate, make use of, model, organize, plan, predict, select, solve, solve, use, utilize</p>
<h3>Analyse</h3>	
<h4>Definition</h4>	<h4>Examples of action verbs</h4>
<p>Breaking materials or concepts into parts, determining how the parts relate to one another or how they interrelate, or how the parts relate to an overall structure or purpose. Mental actions included in this function are <i>differentiating, organizing, and attributing</i>, as well as <i>being able to distinguish between</i> the components or parts. When one is analyzing, he/she can illustrate this mental function by creating spreadsheets, surveys, charts, or diagrams, or graphic representations.</p>	<p>contrast, analyze, assume, breakdown, categorize, classify, compare, diagram, discover, dissect, distinguish, divide, examine, function, illustrate, infer, inspect, outline, simplify, survey, test for</p>
<h3>Evaluate</h3>	
<h4>Definition</h4>	<h4>Examples of action verbs</h4>
<p>Making judgments based on criteria and standards through checking and critiquing. Critiques, recommendations, and reports are some of the products that can be created to demonstrate the processes of evaluation. In the newer taxonomy,</p>	<p>agree, appraise, assess, award, build, choose, compare, conclude, criticize, decide, deduct, defend, derive, determine, develop, disprove, estimate, evaluate, explain, formulate, generate, influence, interpret, justify, mark, measure, modify, prioritize, rate,</p>

<i>evaluating</i> comes before creating as it is often a necessary part of the precursory behavior before one creates something.	recommend, select, support, value
Create	
Definition	Examples of action verbs
Putting elements together to form a coherent or functional whole; reorganizing elements into a new pattern or structure through generating, planning, or producing. Creating requires users to put parts together in a new way, or synthesize parts into something new and different creating a new form or product. This process is the most difficult mental function in the new taxonomy.	adapt, assemble, build, change, choose, collaborate, collect, combine, compile, compile, compose, construct, create, delete, design, develop, develop, devise, elaborate, estimate, formulate, imagine, imagine, improve, invent, makeup, maximize, modify, originate, plan, propose, rearrange, solve, substitute, test

Sources: Definitions adapted from:
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Related articles

Learning Outcomes
 Learning objectives or learning outcomes?

Template

Learning outcomes

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<https://wwwctl.ox.ac.uk/effective-learning-outcomes>

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<https://www.vanderbilt.edu/advanced-institute/>

Keywords

SMART learning outcomes, learning outcomes, Bloom's Revised Taxonomy

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Learning objectives or learning outcomes?

Summary

Learning objectives focus on what instructors intend to teach, while learning outcomes emphasize what learners will achieve. Objectives guide course structure; outcomes support assessment. Choosing between them depends on the course's purpose. Both have their importance for effective course design and clear, meaningful learning experiences.

Main text

Although the terms learning objectives and learning outcomes are often used interchangeably, they represent distinct concepts and serve different functions in course design. **Learning objectives** focus on the trainer's or course designer's intentions—what the course aims to cover and what the trainer plans to deliver. They are the intended results of the instruction and are usually defined at the beginning of the course. On the other hand, **learning outcomes** emphasize what learners are expected to accomplish by the end of the course (knowledge, skills, and attitudes). They center on the learner and highlight measurable achievements.

Fundamentally, the difference lies in their focus and purpose. Learning objectives are trainer-centered and often describe specific teaching activities or plans. Learning outcomes, however, are learner-centered and result-driven.

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While objectives may sometimes be broad or non-measurable, outcomes must always be clearly defined and assessable.

Establishing learning objectives or learning outcomes

Deciding whether to use learning objectives or learning outcomes depends on the goal of the course or lesson. If the main priority is the content to be delivered, learning objectives are more suitable. They help organize the course structure, clarify the instructional approach, and maintain a logical flow throughout the teaching process. However, if the emphasis is on the learner's achievements—such as gaining knowledge, developing specific skills, or adopting new attitudes—then learning outcomes are the better choice. Outcomes are particularly valuable when creating assessment tools or determining if the course successfully meets its goals from the learner's perspective.

For instance, in an online learning environment, if a course is primarily designed to convey foundational knowledge, learning objectives may be sufficient to explain its purpose. However, if the course aims to build practical skills or influence behavioral change, it is essential to establish clear learning outcomes that specify what learners should be able to demonstrate upon completion.

Conclusion

While both learning objectives and learning outcomes are crucial elements of effective course design, they are not identical. Objectives provide direction for teaching, whereas outcomes serve as benchmarks for measuring learner success. Understanding the distinction between the two helps ensure that courses are thoughtfully designed, expectations are clearly communicated, and learners are well-prepared to achieve success. Selecting the appropriate term in the right context leads to clearer communication and more meaningful learning experiences.

Related articles

Learning Outcomes

Effective learning outcomes

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Keywords

learning objectives, learning outcomes, course design

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Assessment methods

Summary

Assessment is the process of documenting the knowledge, skills, attitudes, or beliefs of the learner after they have completed instructional activities. It should be aligned with the learning outcomes established in the beginning of the design process. There are different types of assessment: diagnostic, formative, summative, formal, informal, objective and subjective.

Main text

Determining assessment evidence

Once the desired results are established, it is possible to identify ways to know what the learners know, that is, to determine the acceptable evidence that such results were effectively obtained. Assessment is the term that refers to the activities used to gauge learner's progress. In other words, it represents the methods to collect tangible data in the course in order to monitor whether the learning objectives and outcomes are being fulfilled.

Assessment is, thus, “the process of documenting the knowledge, skills, attitudes, or beliefs of the learner after they have completed instructional activities” (Digital Learning Toolkit).

The scope of the assessment should take into account the balance between knowledge and skills that are reflected in the learning outcomes.

Characteristics of evaluation: validity and reliability

Effective assessments are both reliable and valid. “A reliable test means that when it is administered many times to learners who receive the same

instruction, similar results are achieved. A valid test refers to a test that is measuring the desired learning impact” (Digital LearningToolkit). For instance, if the goal is to teach a skill, such as applying metadata, a written test may not measure whether or not the learner can perform the task.

In face-to-face training, learners can give visual cues and engage in casual conversations. Such types of signs indicate if they understand the material or need more guidance. In an online environment these opportunities are more limited, thus having reliable and valid assessments is especially important.

Types of assessment

A learner-centered environment offers different opportunities for learner’s feedback on whether they believe the outcomes are being supported by the course. This means that assessment can occur at various moments, each serving distinct purposes. It can occur before the training or its early stages. Its goal is to gauge the learner’s previous knowledge and readiness for the new content. When occurring during the training, it offers insights in how learners are progressing and allows for adjustments in instruction. Finally, at the end of a unit or course it determines achievement of the learning objectives and outcomes.

- **Diagnostic or pre-assessment** occurs at the beginning of a lesson or unit to gauge students’ prior knowledge and readiness for new material.
- **Formative assessment** takes place during instruction, offering real-time insights into how concepts are being understood and how skills are being acquired. It is a tool for learners to identify areas in which they are excelling as well as where they need more work.
- **Summative assessment, or assessment of learning,** occurs at the end of a lesson, unit, or term. It is used to evaluate overall learner achievement, such as with end-of-unit exams, projects, or standardized state tests.

There are other types of assessment that should also be considered:

- **Formal assessment** is attached to activities that quantify the knowledge

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gained, for instance, taking an exam. A score is usually provided and is used to measure a learner’s performance, which may affect their final grade.

- **Informal assessment** is similar to formal assessments in the sense that they usually provide feedback to the learner and the instructor. The main difference is that the feedback or score does not contribute to a learner’s final grade. They usually occur in a more casual manner and may include observation, inventories, checklists, rating scales, peer and self-evaluation, and discussion.

- **Objective assessment** is a form of questioning which has a single correct answer, such as multiple choice, true/false, and matching, questions. They also provide immediate feedback to the learners so that they can learn from their mistakes and continue working.

- **Subjective assessment** is a form of questioning which may have more than one correct answer, such as essays, short answers, and oral questions. As this type of assessment is more open-ended, it should be evaluated against a set of clearly defined criteria and questions.

Additionally, **self-assessment** is also an important source of feedback for both learners and trainers because it will allow learners to chart their own growth throughout the course and take more ownership of their learning.

Methods of assessment

The assessment can take the form of quizzes, projects, presentations, portfolios, and even tests. However, it is important to keep in mind that assessment does not mean grading. Grades, badges, certifications can be used as a proof of training, but here we are talking about the evidence we will collect for our assessment and how we will collect them throughout the training.

Table 1. Aligning learning outcomes and assessment methods

Learning Outcomes	Verbs	Assessment Methods
Remember	Describe, define,	quizzes, multiple choice,

	identify, label, name, match	true/false questions, journals
Understand	Articulate, contrast, explain	classify, discuss, , concept maps, discussion boards
Apply	Apply, calculate, choose, modify, use	change, construct, predict, solve, case studies
Analyse	Analyse, categorise, debate, experiment, organise	appraise, contrast, examine, case studies, group work
Evaluate	Apraise, critique, estimate, support	assess, contrast, defend, measure, peer review activities, group member evaluation, self-evaluation
Create	animate, create, formulate, produce	design, develop, generate, portfolios, projects, papers

Source: Based on Cornell University, Center for Teaching Innovation: <https://teaching.cornell.edu/assessing-student-learning/learning-outcome-types-and-recommended-assessment-methods>

Related articles

Backward design

Learning outcomes

Learning Experience

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Alignment Grid

Templates

Assessment methods

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Keywords

Assessment

Types of Assessment

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Learning Experience

Summary

Learning experience represents the activities that learners will do during the course and the way trainers can support significant kinds of learning.

In a learner-centered approach, active learning is recommended because it involves the learners in both doing and thinking about the things they are doing. Active learning includes three methods:

- receiving information and ideas,
- doing and observing,
- reflecting.

Main text

Once learning outcomes are established and the best assessment types and methods are identified, it is time to describe what the learners will do during the course and how trainers can support significant kinds of learning. In other words, this is the phase where the most appropriate learning and teaching activities are designed.

A very traditional teaching activity consists primarily of an organized summary of the content. In other words, a lecture that could (or not) be followed by a discussion. This kind of learning experience consists of the learner mostly listening, taking notes and sometimes engaging in class discussions. This tradition has been challenged by the concept of active learning for better learning and longer content retention (Fink, 2003).

Active learning is anything that involves the learners in both doing and thinking about the things they are doing. Fink (2003) expands this definition in

order to incorporate what is valid in both traditional and contemporary ideas of teaching and learning. His view includes three methods that make a more complete set of learning experiences: information and ideas, experiences and reflection.

Figure 1. Representation of passive and active learning

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to do (apply standards, make an oral presentation, create a project, etc.).	they are learning (observe a demonstration, observe social, natural or cultural phenomena etc.).	learning, alone and with others.
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Source: based on Fink (2003) *Creating significant learning experiences: an integrated approach to designing college courses*

This view of active learning suggests that an effective set of learning activities is one that includes activities from each of the three components of active learning: information and ideas, experiences, and reflection. Secondly, although direct ways of providing these three forms of learning are preferable, indirect and even distance learning forms can be provided.

Table 1. Learning activities that promote active learning

	Information and Ideas	Experiences “Doing”	Experiences “Observing”	Reflection
Direct	Original data Original sources	Real doing in authentic settings	Direct observation of practices and phenomena	Classroom discussions Term papers In-depth reflective dialogue and writing on the learning process
Indirect	Secondary data and sources Lectures, textbooks	Case studies Simulations	Stories (via film, literature, oral history)	-

Distance learning	Course Website Internet Video lectures Web-conference	Trainer can assign learners to directly experience Learners can engage in indirect kinds of experience at distant sites or online.	Learners can record their reflections and then, if they choose, share them
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Source: based on Fink (2003) *Creating significant learning experiences: an integrated approach to designing college courses*

Related articles

Backward design

Learning outcomes

Assessment methods

Alignment grid

Templates

Learning Experience

References

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Keywords

Active learning

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Alignment and course blueprint

Summary

The alignment between the essential intent of the course, learning objectives, learning activities and learner assessment guides your designing work to ensure a meaningful learning experience. Once alignment is secured, it is time to prepare a course plan, or course blueprint. Key elements of a blueprint include:

- Course information
- Course learning objectives and outcomes
- Lesson topics and format
- Learning resources
- Activities and assessment
- Information about learners
- Information about trainers

Main text

Alignment refers to how critical course elements work together to promote students' achievement of the intended learning outcomes. The learning outcomes form the spine of a course, holding together the corresponding elements that must be aligned: assessments that appropriately measure learners' attainment of intended outcome and the most appropriate modes of instruction.

Proper alignment avoids including topics that teach topics that are not necessary, suggesting activities that are irrelevant to the learning process and,

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what would be more serious, assessing learners on topics that may not have necessarily been covered. Lack of alignment can cause, among other issues, a motivation problem.

Once alignment is secured, it is time to consider the context for implementation and delivery. These elements will constitute a course plan, or course blueprint. It enables you to design with the big picture in mind ensuring each milestone is reached and building consistency throughout the curriculum.

Key elements of a blueprint include:

1. Course information
2. Course learning objectives and outcomes
3. Lesson topics and format
4. Learning resources
5. Activities and assessment
6. Information about learners
7. Information about trainers

1. Course Information consists of basic elements about the course. It includes:

- Course title
- Course description
- Degree/certification program, if it is the case
- Required prerequisites and level if learners need to demonstrate previous knowledge, if the course is for beginner, intermediate or advanced level.
- Duration of the course

2. List of learning objectives and outcomes provides a foundation for the course curriculum for learners to reach the instructional goals and ensures that the instructor is building a learning experience consistent with the goals of the overarching program or degree plan.

3. Course format includes face-to-face courses and different types of online training.

- Synchronous Training: Training that occurs in real time, where learners and instructors interact simultaneously, either in person or via live online

platforms (e.g., Zoom, Teams). It allows immediate feedback and real-time discussions.

- **Asynchronous Training:** Training that does not require real-time interaction. Learners access materials (e.g., videos, readings, quizzes) at their own convenience, allowing for flexible, on-demand learning.

- **Tutor-Led Training:** A form of guided learning where an instructor or tutor delivers content and supports learners through direct teaching, explanations, and answering questions. It can be delivered synchronously (live sessions) or asynchronously (recorded lectures with ongoing tutor support).

- **Self-Paced Training:** Training where learners progress through the material at their own speed, without a fixed schedule. It is typically asynchronous and allows learners to control their own learning timeline based on personal needs and availability.

- **Hybrid Training:** A blended approach that combines elements of both synchronous and asynchronous training, and may also mix tutor-led and self-paced components. For example, learners might attend live virtual sessions while also completing online modules independently.

4. Resources help the learner to understand knowledge and practice and apply concepts. Resources include course texts, online resources, presentations, multimedia assets, interactive material, among other types.

Resources can be created from scratch or reused. Considering existing resources, they can be categorised into two broad groups: actual training material and other resources that can be turned into training material.

It is also important to consider what kind of resources and tools are necessary such as computers, internet connection, a specific software, etc.

5. Activities and assignments regard the assessment methods already identified.

6. Information about learners includes the number of participants. Synchronous training (face to face or online) is more effective if the groups are smaller, allowing for better interaction. Self-paced on-line training does not require a fixed limit of participants. It is also important to consider if participants need to present previous knowledge on the topic and if they need to be pre-assessed to confirm such knowledge.

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Finally, diversity should also be considered. Diversity is not only about gender or race, but also level and domain of expertise, professional experience, roles, etc.

7. Information about the trainer, or the role of the trainer, depends on the modality of the delivery. Tutor-led training requires a greater engagement of the training during implementation. In self-paced experiences, trainers can track learner progress as they make their way through a module or course, and keep track of any drop of points, or areas where learners may need more attention and assistance.

8. Type of licence and access, for dissemination, sharing and reuse of the training material.

Related articles

Backward design

Learning outcomes

Assessment Methods

Learning Experience

Templates

Course Blueprint

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Keywords

Alignment, course blueprint

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Training Development

Summary

The development stage turns that blueprint into a tangible learning experience. It unfolds in three phases:

- Prototype creation,
- Course development and
- Test run.

Main text

Once you've defined your audience, learning goals, and overall plan in the Analyze and Design stages, the Development stage turns that blueprint into a tangible learning experience. It unfolds in three phases:

1. Prototype Creation

A small, varied sample of course pages (e.g., text, media, and interactive content) is created to demonstrate the course structure and design. A short course plan summary can accompany it for co-design actions and evaluation. This helps ensure alignment before full development begins.

2. Course Development

Course materials are created using diverse formats—text, videos, graphics, interactive elements—to maintain engagement and support learning. Content should follow a logical progression and always stay aligned with the course's objectives and learning outcomes. Feedback from earlier stages should be incorporated throughout.

Ongoing testing and review of course modules ensure accuracy, usability, and

alignment with learning goals. Breaking content into sections allows for parallel development and review, streamlining feedback loops and ensuring quality without slowing progress.

3. Test Run

Selected learners go through the developed course sections. Their feedback is used to identify and fix issues through multiple iterations. Completion times are tracked to ensure the course meets time and learning expectations.

Templates

Training development checklist

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Keywords

Prototype creation,
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Training Implementation

Summary

Implementation marks the first time the target audience interacts with the course content and activities. Two different training formats have an impact on the implementation of the course: tutor-led training and self-paced training. In tutor-led training, trainers support learners by guiding the learning process, encouraging interaction, and prompting reflection. Self-paced training requires a strong community, support, checkpoints and an evaluation system.

Main text

Implementation marks the first time the target audience interacts with the course content and activities. One of the critical components for a successful learning experience is effective facilitation of the course. The learners should be able to absorb the information presented and share their interpretations and knowledge with their peers so that the online environment feels like a collaborative community (Digital LLearning Toolkit).

Two different training formats have an impact on the implementation of the course: tutor-led training and self-paced training.

Tutor-led training

Trainers, instructors and facilitators have an important role and it can be the single largest influencer of learning and the learner experience. Learning, online or in face-to-face classrooms, does not happen in isolation. Trainers should support learners by guiding the learning process, encouraging

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interaction, and prompting reflection.

Trainers can facilitate learning in different ways. The facilitation starts by **welcoming course participants** (before the event via an welcome email or video and in the beginning of the course. It is the moment to describe the course and summarize learning outcomes. Schedules and important dates should be informed as well as any requirements to complete the course. It is also an opportunity to get to know the participants, asking them to introduce themselves, verify their previous knowledge about the topic and expectations about the course.

Building community is equally important during a course, especially if it is an online training and participants might feel isolated. Regular and open communication with learners about the status of their performance and opportunities for feedback help to build trust and improve engagement.

Creating spaces for discussion provides an opportunity for learners to get to know each other and the trainer and helps to **connect**. Such spaces also provide a way for the trainers to model behaviour in interactions. Trainers and facilitators should check regularly how the discussions progress in such spaces, ensuring responses are appropriate and relevant and the environment is respectful and friendly. It is important to maintain a balance between meeting learning outcomes and sustaining the health of a community.

Finally, the trainer should **participate actively** and be present during the whole course. Trainers' role is to lead, motivate, nurture, and stimulate both the group and the individuals participating in the course. Publicly acknowledging learners when their contributions are particularly strong and also motivating less advanced learners with positive reinforcements are ways to recognize their effort and motivate their engagement.

Use expected responses to activities to **challenge learners** and encourage deeper reflection about the topic. Also, involving learners as co-facilitators is a good strategy to help them put into practice the recently acquired knowledge.

Self-paced training

Self-paced training is a format that includes a variety of activities and

assignments for learners to complete in their own time. In this format, learners are not required to participate on specific dates and times, they can make progress on their own pace and terms.

Self-paced learning is an individualized process, but it does not mean it should be done in isolation. Isolation can actually hurt engagement and completion rates.

Self-paced training also benefits from having a **strong community** where learners can ask questions and find support.

Virtual checkpoints at specific moments can give learners the opportunity to interact with other course participants and, if possible, with an instructor or facilitator.

Support should be offered via an email or any other kind of tool that allows learners to get help when in need.

Finally it is essential to put a system in place that **evaluates** learners and tracks course progress.

Templates

Training implementation checklist

References

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Evaluation

Summary

Evaluation is a critical part of the teaching and learning processes as it helps teachers and instructors to determine if the learners have understood the content presented to them. It also helps learners to gauge their own level of understanding. Evaluation is not the end of the training development and implementation, but the starting point for the next iteration. Thorough evaluation enables training developers and facilitators to review and improve the programme. The terms “assessment” and “evaluation” are often used interchangeably, but they each have distinct definitions.

Main text

Evaluation is a critical part of the teaching and learning process. It completes the feedback loop, and helps teachers and instructors to determine if the learners have understood the content presented to them. It also helps learners to gauge their own level of understanding. Evaluation is also a tool to improve facilitation and the course design as it shows how well learners have engaged with the subject matter

It is noteworthy that the terms “assessment” and “evaluation” are often used interchangeably, but they each have distinct definitions (Digital Learning Toolkit):

- **Assessment** refers to how tangible data is collected in the course in order to monitor whether the learning objectives and outcomes are being fulfilled. Simply stated, assessments determine what students learned and how they learned it.

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- **Evaluation** refers to your overall judgment on whether the course has met the learning outcomes and objectives you conveyed at the beginning of the course.

Evaluating training at the end is a crucial step because it helps ensure that the training is effective, efficient, and aligned with the learning objectives and outcomes.

The evaluation phase is important because it verifies if (McDonald and West, 2021):

- the instructional goals are aligned with the requirements of the instructional program;
- the lesson plans, instructional materials, media, and assessments are aligned with the learning needs;
- any changes to the design are necessary in order to improve the effectiveness and overall satisfaction with the instruction;
- the implementation provides effective instruction and carries out the intended lesson plan and instructional objectives;
- the learners obtained the knowledge and skills that they needed;
- the learners are able to transfer their learning into the desired contextual setting.

These points show that the evaluation phase does not need to happen at the last stage of training design, rather it will ideally happen throughout the whole process.

Conclusion

Evaluation appears as the final stage of the design process, however, it should not be seen as its conclusion. Evaluation is rather a starting point for the next iteration of the training development and implementation. Diligent evaluation enables training developers and facilitators to review and improve the programme.

Templates

Evaluation

Related material

Assessment

Designing evaluation questions

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Further reading

“An Introduction to Evaluating Your Teaching.” n.d. Accessed July 20, 2025.
<https://wwwctl.ox.ac.uk/evaluating-teaching>.

Keywords

evaluation, assessment

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Designing Evaluation Questions

Summary

Different types of questions can be used to evaluate the impact of the course material and implementation on learning. The types of questions chosen depend on what the training designer or facilitator wants to find out. Some examples are multiple choice questions, Likert scale and open-ended questions.

Main text

Different types of questions can be used to evaluate the impact of the course material and implementation on learning. The types of questions chosen depend on what the training designer or facilitator wants to find out.

Types of questions

1. Multiple choice questionnaire

Forms that give learners a range of choices also prompt reflection and can be quickly completed. They are useful when the training designer or facilitator is looking for feedback on specific aspects of the teaching or learning. It can be done after an individual session, series of sessions or across a whole course.

For example:

Which of the following did you find most engaging during the course?

- Group presentations
- Discussion with peers

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- Facilitator activity
- Exercises
- Other (please specify)

2. Likert scale questions

Likert scale questions ask learners to respond on a numerical scale of 1 ('strongly disagree') to 5 ('strongly agree'), rather than a simple "yes" or "no". The questions can be asked about individual sessions or modules or after the completion of a whole course or programme.

Examples of statements:

The reading list has been helpful for my assignments

The examples provided have helped me to understand key concepts

I was given opportunities to provide feedback on the course

The statements can also be used to help learners to reflect about their own engagement and learning. For example:

I have come to each session well prepared to participate.

I have completed the assignments after each session.

Evaluation forms that use Likert scales will give an overview of what is helping and hindering learning; however, it will not clarify the reasons. For instance, if learners disagree with the statement that "The session was at the right pace", such disagreement does not clarify if the pace was too fast or too slow. Including an additional open-ended question that allows learners to elaborate on their responses can therefore be important.

3. General open-ended questions

Open-ended questions can help learners to reflect about the learning process and what they need to do next. It also gives designers or facilitators important

information that can lead to training improvement. These questions can be used to evaluate individual sessions or modules or the whole training.

For example:

How will you use your learning from today in your daily work activities? What aspect(s) of today's session particularly helped your learning? (For instance, the way the facilitator introduced the concepts, the group discussion, the link established today's content and previous content, etc.) What aspect(s) of today's session are you least confident about? (For example, is there a task you don't know how to complete, is there any concept that does not seem relevant, etc.)

Templates

Evaluation

Related material

Assessment

Evaluation

References

"Designing Evaluation Questions." n.d. Accessed July 20, 2025.
<https://www.ctl.ox.ac.uk/designing-evaluation-questions>.

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Templates

Framework Category	Templates
Analysis	Needs analysis Learners analysis Task analysis
Design	Learning outcomes Assessment Learning experience Alignment Course blueprint
Development	Training development checklist
Implementation	Training implementation checklist
Evaluation	Evaluation

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Needs Analysis

Step 1 - Problem Identification: Verify if training is justified

This step helps to identify whether the problem can be solved or an opportunity can be seized through training.

1. Consider your context

Check the one that applies:

Are you considering developing training for your organization?	Do you need to develop training in the framework of a funded project?	Are you considering developing training for the users of the service you provide?	Other ?
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2. Identify the goals

Tip 1: When verifying if training is necessary, ask yourself some questions.

Ask the following questions:

- What are the knowledge and skills necessary to achieve the goals?
- What are the needs of the community? What are their current skills?
- Is this training essential, is it in the core of the organisation? Or is the training essential for the users of the service I provide?
- If not, maybe training is not necessary.

→ Training that is really necessary deals with the core activity of the organisation

What are the quantitative (can you quantify the improvement?) and qualitative (can you name, define, list the improvements?) goals and standards?

What are the goals of the organisation? What does the organisation want to achieve (in one year, in five years)?	What is the general objective of the project?	What are the goals of the service? What does the service want to achieve?	Other ?
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Tip: Check the organisation's mission statement and strategic plan.	Tip: Check the grant agreement.	Tip: What is the purpose of the service? Who are the users? What are the service's objectives (roadmap, improvements, etc.)?	
Tip 2: Maybe training is not the answer. You can use other strategies to achieve your goals.			
<p>Some non-training solutions are communication, clarification, job aids.</p> <p>Give feedback, prepare a job aid that can be referred to, automatic reminder (to do perform a task), simplify, improve or eliminate the process, fix usability issues, improve communication and dissemination</p>			

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Step 2 - Identification of data sources

Once training is deemed necessary, the following step is to identify the current state and the desired state of affairs.

Tip 1: Think about the gaps.

Needs analysis can be a process for identifying and measuring differences and inconsistency between what is and what should be at the strategic, tactical, or operational level.

Tip 2: Think about the opportunities too

Needs analysis can also be a process that identifies and highlights the positive achievements, adding valuable information about what is working well and how one can build on those results.

1. Identify the Stakeholders

Identify stakeholder groups: researchers, project partners, community of users, etc.

Identify individuals within stakeholders' groups who are familiar with the topic, care about it.

Some stakeholders in the context of open scholarly communication for the Social Sciences and Humanities can be:

Authors	Editors	Editorial managers	Librarians
Publishers	Translators	SSH researchers	PhD students
Service providers	Police makers	Other	

2. Identify the methods

Select the best methods (e.g., existing data review, interviews, surveys, or focus groups) to collect information about the gap(s). If you are creating new data collection tools, allow time and resources to pilot test with the intended audience.

Evaluation questions may include questions about the gap source and what is needed to close the gaps

Interviews	Focus groups	Surveys	Document analysis
Open Consultation	Other		

Ask Follow up questions

Ask "WHY?" when conducting a needs assessment, ask follow-up questions to help understand why a situation is occurring or what is causing a problem in the organization.

Align needs analysis and constraints

Scale the needs analysis activities based upon the time constraints or resources associated with a project.

Step 3 – Data collection

In this step, data should be collected from different sources with two questions in mind:

- Why aren't people performing as they should?
- What will help people to perform better?

Data collection from multiple sources makes a huge difference when designing training in an informed way because it shows light to different aspects of the current and the desired state of affairs.

Step 4 – Data analysis

This step helps to identify the patterns and key factors influencing the initial problem

The goal when analysing the data is to identify trends, commonalities, or correlations as to why something is or is not happening. That way, it is possible to better identify whether the issue is caused by those four things we talked about before—lack of knowledge, skills, motivation, resources, or something else.

Step 5 – Recommendations

This step aims to compile and prioritize a list of training recommendations based on the organization's or stakeholders' priorities.

What is the problem that training will solve?

Why is training necessary?

Who is the target of the training?

- Consider doing a learners' analysis

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LEARNERS' ANALYSIS

Step 1 – Gather information about the learner

This step helps to identify what type of information³⁴ is necessary to understand the learner and to develop meaningful, relevant, and accessible learning experiences.

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Which of these characteristics are relevant for you?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Size of target audience • Are there any sub-groups that may participate? • Age ranges • Educational/grade level, or academic program year • How long have they been out of an educational setting? • Gender breakdown • Cultural backgrounds, races, ethnicities, nationalities • Primary language | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural views towards education Student/teacher • Employment status • Socioeconomic status • Traditional/non-traditional/ first-generation learner? • Geographic location(s) & time zones • Internet connectivity? Access to technology? • Other? |
|---|--|

LEARNER DETAILS

COGNITIVE & PRIOR KNOWLEDGE CHARACTERISTICS

Which of these characteristics are relevant for you?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education Level and prior achievements • Do they meet prerequisite skills required? | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familiarity with Web 2.0 tools • Online experience • Learning Disabilities • Cognitive Disabilities • Other? |
|--|--|

³⁴ Chart constructed from information found in Smith, P.L., & Ragan, T.J. (2005) *Instructional design* (3rd ed.).

- Prior knowledge/proficiency related to subject/content
- Learning Styles
- Computer/Information literacy

LEARNER DETAILS

PHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Which of these characteristics are relevant for you?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional: beliefs, habits of thinking, curiosity level, creativity • Any medical issues that may impede participation? | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical disabilities • Environmental sensitivities • Other? |
|--|--|

LEARNER DETAILS

AFFECTIVE & SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS

Which of these characteristics are relevant for you?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivation level – is the course required or optional? • Attitudes toward self • Relationships | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interests/hobbies • Other ? |
|--|--|

LEARNER DETAILS

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Step 2 – Identify the data sources and collect the data

In this step, data should be collected with a question in mind:

- Who are the people who need training to change the way they are performing?
-
- Surveys
 - Interviews and focus groups
 - Analyses of career paths or job roles (documentation)
 - Learning analytics from past programs
 - Informal consultations or pilot testing

Now that you have information about the learners, you can use it to describe user groups profiles or to create personas (Steps 3 and 4).

Step 3 – Describe a user group profile

User group profiles are generalised descriptions of specific user segments, highlighting their shared characteristics and contexts of use.

User group :

Main goals	
Prior knowledge and training	
Skills (Digital literacy, use of technology etc.)	
Learning needs	
Constraints and problems	

Step 4 – Create personas

Personas are “detailed descriptions of fictitious yet realistic” learners aiming at promoting “empathy among designers, empowering them to understand user needs, motivations, and behaviours and effectively address them.

Give each persona a name and borrow common traits from real individuals within the group

Name:

You can add a photo to your persona.

Age:

Not mandatory

Other demographic information:

Describe goals, job responsibilities, motivations for participation in a learner experience, job roles, attitude toward workplace training, skills and educational levels and so on

Role:

Background:

Prior knowledge:

Pain points:

Other:

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TASK ANALYSIS		
Step 1 – Identify the main task	Step 2 – Identify the subtasks	Step 3 – Define KSA
This step identifies the global task that has to be performed	This step breaks the task into individual steps needed to complete the task successfully.	This step defines the knowledge, skills an attitude necessary to perform the task
Step 4 – Identify the frequency, order and the conditions to perform the task and subtasks		
This step identifies if the order of the subtasks impacts the result, they frequency in which they are performed and the conditions necessary for its completion.		
How often is the task performed? How often are the subtasks performed?	What are the conditions to perform the task and subtasks? What are the tools and resources necessary?	
Does the order of the subtasks impact the result?	Are there any limiting factors such as system limitation or environmental/cultural issues?	
Where will learners need support? What will be challenging for them?		

Task Priorization

List tasks in order of importance or frequency

High priority task	
Medium priority task	
Low priority task	

Training Implications

Summarize what training is required based on the gaps identified

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LEARNING OUTCOMES

What did the needs analysis (or learners' analysis or task analysis) tell you?

What should learners accomplish at the end of the training?

If possible, classify the learning objectives according to their type.

Complete the sentence:

At the end of the training, learners will be able to...

Knowledge-based

Skill-based

Attitude-based

Make sure each of the learning outcomes is **SMART**

- Are they specific and well-defined?
- Are they measurable?
- Are they applicable?
- Are they realistic?
- Are they time-bound?

Check the list of verbs to help you

Source: Based on

<https://teaching.utoronto.ca/resources/active-verbs-for-blooms-revised-taxonomy/>

Assessment

How are you going to verify that learners have acquired new knowledge and learned how to perform new tasks?

Copy the learning outcomes here

Before the training starts

Do learners need to demonstrate prior knowledge before engaging in activities to acquire new knowledge and skills?

If so, describe this knowledge

How is it going to be verified?

What will the pre-assessment look like?

During the training

What methods are you going to use to verify how concepts are being understood and how skills are being acquired? How can learners identify areas in which they are excelling as well as where they need more work?

For each learning outcome, establish specific assessment methods

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What will the formative assessment look like?	
Learning outcomes	Assessment methods Check the table below for support.

Learning Outcomes	Verbs	Assessment Methods
Remember	Describe, define, identify, label, name, match	quizzes, multiple choice, true/false questions, journals
Understand	Articulate, classify, contrast, discuss, explain	quizzes, multiple choice, , concept maps, discussion boards
Apply	Apply, calculate, change, choose, construct, modify, predict, solve, use	problem sets, case studies
Analyse	Analyse, appraise, categorise, contrast, debate, examine, experiment, organise	case studies, group work
Evaluate	Apraise, assess, contrast, critique, defend, estimate, measure, support	peer review activities, group member evaluation, self-evaluation
Create	animate, arrange, create, design, develop, formulate, generate, produce	portfolios, projects, papers

LEARNING EXPERIENCE

What activities will learners do during the course to achieve their outcomes?

What can trainers do to support significant kinds of learning?

Types of activities

Receive information

Do experiences
and
Reflect about experiences

Copy the learning outcomes here

Type of activity

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Course Blueprint

Course title	
Description	The description of the course summarizes all important information about the training, such as, the context of its development, its global goal, the target audience, the format, and information about sessions and modules if it is the case.
Required prerequisites / level	Do learners need to demonstrate previous knowledge? Is the course for beginner, intermediate or advanced learners?
Duration	Duration of the programme, but it can also include the duration of each session or module.
Course objectives	What are the objectives of the course or programme?
Learning outcomes	What will learners be able to do at the end of the training?
Course format	Is the training face to face or online? Is it synchronous or asynchronous? Is it tutored-led or self-paced? Is it hybrid
Resources	Resources include course texts, online resources, presentations, multimedia assets, interactive material, among other types. It also includes what kind of resources and tools are necessary such as computers, internet connection, a specific software, etc.
Activities and assessment	List of activities and assessments that will be carried out during the training
Participants	Target audience (roles, background), number of participants, diversity aspects sought
Trainer / Facilitator	Information about the role of the trainer
Type of licence	Open licences are recommended

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Course Blueprint	
Course title	
Description	
Required prerequisites / level	
Duration	
Course objectives	
Learning outcomes	
Course format	
Resources	
Activities and assessment	
Participants	
Trainer / Facilitator	
Type of licence	

Training Development checklist

1. Create a Prototype

- Prepare a small sample (2–3 pages) with varied layouts (e.g., text-only, media-rich, interactive).
- Write a concise summary of the course plan (1–2 pages).
- Include the educational strategy developed during the Design phase.
- Share the prototype and plan with stakeholders for co-design, review and approval.

2. Develop the Course

Content creation

- Use a mix of content types (text, visuals, video, infographics, interactive tasks).
- Content can be made from scratch or reused.
- Organize content logically (introductory → intermediate → advanced).
- Align content with intended learning outcomes
- Integrate findings and needs identified in the Analysis stage.
- Keep lessons concise and avoid dense, dry text blocks.
- Check FAIR-by-Design methodology³⁵ for content creation.

Integrate Active Learning Strategies

- Design activities aligned with learning outcomes (according to Bloom's Revised Taxonomy)
- Provide varied opportunities to do and observe experiences and to reflect about such experiences
- Include learner-centered tasks like concept mapping, case studies, and scenario-based exercises.
- Add interactive elements (quizzes, polls, reflections, discussions).
- Utilize tools for feedback and peer learning (rubrics, forums, self-assessments).

Quality Assurance

- Divide the course into modules or sections.
- Submit each module for review upon completion.

³⁵ https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/FAIR-by-Design_Book/

- Address feedback iteratively while continuing development.
- If possible, use QA professionals or peers to catch errors (content, technical, accessibility).

3. Conduct a Test Run

- Select sample learners to complete the finished modules.
- Gather detailed feedback on usability, content clarity, and engagement.
- Measure time spent vs. expected duration.
- Make necessary revisions and re-test if needed.
- Submit the full course for final stakeholder review and sign-off

Implementation checklist

Tutor-Led Training Checklist

Before the Course

- Send a welcome email or video to participants
- Ask learners to introduce themselves
- Gauge participants' prior knowledge and expectations

Beginning of the course (first day)

- Introduce the course and summarize learning outcomes
- Share the course schedule and important dates
- Inform participants about course requirements (e.g., assignments, assessments)
- Do another set of introductions if necessary

During the Course

- Foster interaction and guide the learning process actively
- Encourage reflection through questions or discussion prompts
- Maintain regular communication with learners
- Provide feedback and updates on learner performance
- Create and moderate discussion spaces for participants
- Monitor discussions to ensure respectful, relevant engagement
- Balance course progression with community well-being
- Actively participate and remain present throughout the course
- Publicly acknowledge strong contributions
- Offer encouragement and reinforcement to less confident learners
- Use expected responses to challenge learners and promote deeper thinking
- Involve learners as co-facilitators to reinforce knowledge application

Self-Paced Training Checklist

Design and Setup

- Provide a variety of activities and assignments for learners
- Ensure learners can access all materials at their own pace
- Include clear guidance on how to progress through the course

Supporting Learners

- Create a strong support system to prevent learner isolation
- Establish a virtual community or forum for questions and peer support
- Schedule optional virtual checkpoints for group interaction
- Offer support via email or messaging tools for individual questions

Monitoring and Evaluation

- Implement a system to track learner progress
- Include mechanisms to evaluate learning outcomes

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Evaluation		
<p>Tip: Dos</p> <p>Phrase questions which ask students to elaborate or give examples</p> <p>Ask complementary questions like “Why?”</p>		
<p>Tip: Donts</p> <p>Avoid general questions that ask for “yes” or “no”.</p> <p>This type of questions won’t give you enough information to act on</p>		
Type of question:	Multiple choice questions	
Definition	Use it when	Example
Questions that give learners a range of choices also prompt reflection and can be quickly completed.	looking for feedback on specific aspects of the teaching or learning	<p>What type of activity do you prefer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercises to complete at home • Group discussions during the sessions • Etc.
Type of question	Likert scale	
Definition	Use it when	Example
Question to be responded on a numerical scale of 1 (‘strongly disagree’) to 5 (‘strongly agree’).	looking for an overview of what is helping and hindering learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am satisfied with this course. • I would recommend this course. • The activities were carried out at an adequate pace. • Etc.
Type of question	Open-ended question	
Definition	Use it when	Example
Questions that allow learners to reflect about the learning process and what they need to do next.	Looking for more in-depth feedback.	Did you have the time to complete the self-paced part prior to the live session? How much time did it take you to complete all the content on the self-paced part?

After the training

Is there going to be an overall evaluation of learner's achievement, such as with end-of-unit exams or final projects?

A summative assessment is not mandatory.

Will there be a summative assessment?

If so, what will it look like?

Final remarks

There are other types of assessment

Assessment can be:

- Formal
- Informal
- Objective
- Subjective

Include self-assessment

Important source of feedback for both learners and trainers because it will allow learners to chart their own growth throughout the course and take more ownership of their learning.

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Annex 6: Collaboration checklist

ADDIE Stage	Key Goals	Possible Collaborators	Checklist
Analyze	Identify training needs, learner profiles, and context	Researchers, data stewards, community leads, National Nodes representatives, institutional partners	<input type="checkbox"/> Have we consulted key stakeholders to identify needs? <input type="checkbox"/> Have we documented learner personas and goals? <input type="checkbox"/> Are data collection tools shared and transparent?
Design	Define learning objectives, training structure, and methods	Instructional designers, accessibility experts, subject matter experts, trainers, OS officers	<input type="checkbox"/> Are learning outcomes co-developed? <input type="checkbox"/> Have we aligned methods with learner needs? <input type="checkbox"/> Are roles for design clearly assigned?
Develop	Create and review content, tools, and resources	Content creators, technical staff, translators, reviewers	<input type="checkbox"/> Is content development distributed? <input type="checkbox"/> Are contributions peer-reviewed? <input type="checkbox"/> Is the development process documented and versioned?
Implement	Deliver and facilitate the training effectively	Trainers, facilitators, national nodes representatives, communication officers	<input type="checkbox"/> Are delivery responsibilities shared? <input type="checkbox"/> Is infrastructure in place for joint implementation? <input type="checkbox"/> Are feedback channels open?
Evaluate	Collect feedback, assess impact, and improve training	Evaluators, quality assurance staff, trainers, learners	<input type="checkbox"/> Are evaluation metrics co-defined? <input type="checkbox"/> Is impact data shared across partners? <input type="checkbox"/> Have we planned a joint review or reflection?